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Deliverable 7.7
Plan for Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation of Project Results (PEDR)

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The main work on this deliverable report was performed by BNN, task leader of Task 7.4 in WP7 on “Innovation Management: Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation”. Susanne Resch, scientific researcher at BNN, developed the overall communication and dissemination strategy within the DIAGONAL project. [It is currently managed by Caitlin Ahern, supported by Barbara Ebner \(Haupt\) and Simone Jagersbacher](#), graphic design and communication specialists at BNN. All project partners contributed input to the content that fed into the creation of the DIAGONAL PEDR.

Abbreviations

EU NSC	...	European NanoSafety Cluster
CoRs	...	Communities of Research
GDPR	...	General Data Protection Regulation
GP	...	General Public
HARNs	...	High Aspect Ratio Nanoparticles
IC	...	Industry, innovation community and industry associations
IG	...	Interest Groups and NGOs
IPR	...	Intellectual Property Rights
KPI	...	Key Performance Indicator
MCNMs	...	Multi-component nanomaterials
NGOs	...	Non-governmental organizations
PEDR	...	Plan for Exploitation and Dissemination of Results
RC	...	Research Community
R&D(&I)	...	Research and Development (and Innovation)
REACH	...	Registration, Evaluation, Authorization and Restriction of Chemicals
SMEs	...	Small and medium-sized enterprises
SRB	...	Standardization and Regulatory Bodies
S&TC	...	Scientific and Technical Committee
WP	...	Work Package

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Introduction

Professional communication, dissemination and exploitation are key elements to ensure that research projects' activities and results generate long-term impact. Effective communication and dissemination of project outcomes ensure the further use of generated results and maximize DIAGONAL's impact.

Within the DIAGONAL work plan, WP7 led by BRI is focused on "Innovation Management: Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation". One main aim of WP7, especially Task 7.4 on "Communication and Dissemination" led by BNN, is to ensure a consistent communication and dissemination of the project's activities and results, safeguarding optimal visibility and both a European and worldwide outreach to all relevant stakeholders (R&D community, industry, regulatory bodies and general society).

Deliverable 7.7 "Plan for Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation of Project Results (PEDR)" directly serves to achieve the following specific objectives within WP7:

- Communication, creating visibility and encouraging project outreach.
- Disseminating results to targeted stakeholders and the scientific community.
- Exploitation of results to foster innovation potential and innovation capacity.

Description of Task

The DIAGONAL PEDR is part of Task 7.4 on "Communication and Dissemination".

The aim of this Task is to plan, monitor and implement all project's communication and dissemination activities as well as scientific publications. All Consortium partners contribute to this task. BNN as Task 7.4 leader coordinates the overall activities and will evaluate and optimize the project's dissemination performance on regular basis. Internal updates and evaluations on the PEDR were planned for M18, M36 and M42. [Due to a shift in the reporting period, the document was updated in M18, M32 and M42.](#)

Task 7.4 specifically addresses the following topics (as described in the DIAGONAL Grant Agreement):

"T7.4 will ensure appropriate communication and dissemination of DIAGONAL activities, its progress and results. Task leader BNN will coordinate all related activities, all project partners will contribute. The planned communication and dissemination activities will feed into the initial PEDR (Plan of Communication, Exploitation and Dissemination of Results) (D7.7).

All performed and planned actions will be monitored on an annual basis and will consider T7.2. inputs as soon as the results are produced regarding social acceptance. Basic communication means will include a public project website, project factsheets, press releases, participation and contribution to scientific conferences, the use of social media and the creation of scientific publications. BNN produces and publishes an e-newsletter four times a year with an established group of recipients. DIAGONAL will contribute to this useful means of dissemination, by adding project-related news, activities and results (e.g., recent publications) to this newsletter.

A project website, registered with an 'eu' domain name, will be developed by UBU in order to provide a continuous update on the project progress, results, all public deliverables and publications (Open Access). The website will be maintained and updated regularly, and will remain active after the project with adapted content under the responsibility of the project coordinator.

The key scientific results will be published by the project partners of the consortium. DIAGONAL will ensure Open Access for all its publications, which is coordinated in this task by BNN. In addition to making selected publications available via Gold Open Access, public data and all publications emerging from DIAGONAL will be made freely available via public repositories and on the project website.

Proper data management will ensure efficient and ethical handling and use of the primary results as defined in the Data Management Plan (D2.1).

The American partner VIREO will participate in the dissemination of findings in the US, through established networks such as the EU/US Communities of Research, in quarterly newsletters, and through social media, including LinkedIn, Twitter, and blog posts.”

The PEDR summarizes the strategy and concrete actions that the DIAGONAL Consortium follow in order to communicate, disseminate and exploit the project and its results, aiming to help maximize the impact of the project. The communication plan is integrated in the PEDR to increase the reciprocal impacts.

The PEDR serves as a guideline for the Consortium for the communication, dissemination and exploitation activities carried out during the entire DIAGONAL project runtime, ensuring that the project partners take a proactive role in the effort to maximize the outreach of the project by participating in relevant activities (e.g., workshops, conferences, exhibitions, industrial fairs/trade fairs, webinars, trainings, bilateral discussions, public events, etc.), as well as publishing project results in relevant journals and conferences to allow high international visibility of the project. This task also tracks publications to ensure compliance with open access requirements.

Projects results play a key role for communication, dissemination and exploitation and they are essential when performing any relevant activities. Generally, the term 'results' within H2020 projects is defined as “any tangible or intangible output of the action, such as data, knowledge and information whatever their form or nature, whether or not they can be protected, which are generated in the action as well as any attached rights, including intellectual property rights.”¹ This includes all project outcomes that may be used by the project partners or relevant stakeholders. Furthermore, they can be commercially exploited (i.e., products/services/tools) or act as starting point for further research (e.g., data, knowledge, technology, methods, etc.).

¹ EC Research & Innovation Participant Portal Glossary, Reference Terms.

<https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/support/glossary>

In DIAGONAL, communication and dissemination inform the nanosafety research community as well as industry and regulatory bodies on project outcomes relevant for the topic Safe-and-Sustainable-by-Design of complex nanomaterials (such as multicomponent nanomaterials (MCNMs) or high aspect ratio nanoparticles (HARNs)) and other advanced materials. The communication and dissemination strategy ensures that all knowledge generated during the lifetime of the project is successfully disseminated/transferred to the most appropriate target groups. All forms of communication employed, including for example production of newsletter articles by BNN, are designed to reach a global audience.

The impact of the PEDR is measured using appropriate indicators for each action. This document serves as a “living document” throughout the project, guiding the communication and dissemination effort carried out by the consortium. At the end of the project, all the dissemination and communication activities carried out for all relevant stakeholders will be summarized in the final technical report.

D7.7 is structured to move from a general perspective to a detailed plan of action. After a short description of the DIAGONAL project and the objectives of this PEDR, the section ‘results’ presents the communication, dissemination and exploitation plans. Subsection 1.1, ‘Communication and dissemination tools’ concerns the materials that will be used for communication and dissemination purposes. Subsection 1.2 addresses the project stakeholders, with an initial identification of the main ones. Subsection 1.3 addresses the DIAGONAL communication and dissemination strategy in detail and presents an overview of planned activities including conferences, workshops and meetings, networking activities, publications and social media activities. Finally, an approach to the exploitation of the project results is given.

Description of Action

Project Background and Objectives

This section was removed in the M42 Update to save space. To view the project background and objectives, please see D7.7 and D7.7 – M18 Update.

Objectives of the Plan for the Dissemination and Exploitation of Results (PEDR)

The aim of this PEDR is to bring the project's aims and objectives to the attention of targeted stakeholders, thus maximizing the potential of the project results beyond its lifetime.

The objectives of the PEDR are therefore to:

- Raise public awareness about the project, its expected outcomes within defined target groups, using effective communication means and tools;
- Disseminate for understanding: Inform the audiences that potentially benefit from the project outcomes. It is important that these audiences have a clear understanding of what DIAGONAL is focusing on;
- Disseminate to maximize knowledge diffusion across Europe and internationally;
- Exchange experience with related projects and groups working in the field such as the European NanoSafety Cluster (EU NSC), to capture synergies, minimize duplication of work and maximize collaboration potential;
- Disseminate for action to those groups that can influence and bring about change in their organisations. Target groups include the R&D industry, SMEs, NGOs, consumers, regulatory and policy agencies, insurers, etc.;
- Disseminate for marketing, to bring DIAGONAL outcomes to the marketplace. Target groups here are academic as well as industrial end users;
- Ensure open access to all peer-reviewed scientific publications relating to the project results;
- Utilize project results in further research activities other than those covered by the action concerned, or in developing, creating and marketing a product or process, or in creating and providing a service, or in standardization activities.

Results

Communication and Dissemination Plan

An integrated communication campaign was designed and launched by BNN with input from the Consortium utilizing a variety of instruments to communicate the project's success stories and the overall project concept. Through the exploitation of mainstream communication channels, the Consortium strove to increase awareness and enhance societal perception on how Research and Innovation can tackle emerging challenges and positively impact society, while increasing visibility and information flow on the vital role of H2020 and EU-funded research in realizing and achieving ambitious EU-side societal, economic and sustainable growth goals. The communication plan has been continuously updated to integrate the findings of the stakeholder and acceptance analyses (T7.2), implementing communication measures and tools to maximize social acceptance considering cognitive and awareness raising issues as well as risk perceptions.

The main goals of the communication activities are to:

- Promote the project goals, developments and results.
- Provide targeted information to multiple audiences (including the media and the public), in a strategic and effective manner.
- Inform and reach out to society as a whole.
- Communicate how EU funding contributes to tackling societal challenges.

The DIAGONAL communication campaign instruments include (i) the development of a Corporate Identity (logos and layouts) that was developed by M2, (ii) a dedicated website operational from M4 and for two years after the project's ending, (iii) social media channels such as Twitter and LinkedIn that will be up and running from M3, (iv) newsletter contributions, (v) press releases and appropriate material to engage media and journalists, (vi) participation and presentation of the project and its results in Innovation and Networking events and technological fairs and exhibitions, (vii) participation and presentation of the project in other networks and groups, not directly linked to the project, where project partners have strong links and involvement, (viii) in-house presentations to existing clients and collaborators and brainstorming for further extending DIAGONAL solutions to other applications and markets, (ix) a webinar and video introducing potential end-users to the DIAGONAL SSbD Decision Support Tool, (x) fact sheets and quizzes for familiarizing the general public with basic foundational concepts of DIAGONAL (e.g. nanomaterials, nanosafety).

Communication & Dissemination Tools

Effectiveness in reaching the target audiences and the impact of the communication and dissemination activities will be assessed on a regular basis as the project progresses, e.g., in regular bimonthly organized WP2/7 meetings. By combining the meetings of both work packages, we were able to better align communication and dissemination initiatives to each stakeholder group and to take insights from NMBP-16 sister projects and communicate them beyond the project ambassadors.

The developed tools are presented below. All materials used for the communication and dissemination activities reflect a common visual identity, which is associated with the very first visual identity materials developed, i.e., the project logo.

Project Logo

As a first step of the project branding, a project logo was designed (see Figure 3-6). The logo variations are publicly accessible at the project website.²

Figure 1. DIAGONAL logo.

Figure 2. DIAGONAL logo inverted.

² <https://www.diagonalproject.eu/downloads/>

Figure 3. DIAGONAL logo black.

Figure 4. DIAGONAL logo white.

Project Website

All information regarding the project website, accessible at <https://www.diagonalproject.eu/>, is presented in detail in Deliverable 7.6 “Public DIAGONAL website”. The project website was launched in August 2021, i.e., in month 4 of the project runtime.

Project Brand Guideline

To create a recognizable project brand and a coherent image when communicating, a brand guideline for the project has been implemented, which shows how to use the DIAGONAL

brand and its components such as fonts, colours and images. It is publicly available at the project webpage³.

Communication Toolkit & Dissemination Package

The DIAGONAL “Communication Toolkit” is a collection of materials (created by project partner BNN, in conjunction with the project coordinator) that focus on results and outputs over the course of the project. This material is used to support communication and dissemination activities.

The DIAGONAL “Communication Toolkit” compiles a set of templates that are used by all project partners for internal and external communication purposes (i.e., (i) presentation slides and (ii) Deliverable report). These two template documents are presented in Annex 2.

All communication and dissemination activities developed by partners in DIAGONAL have been properly registered through the templates that have been prepared for this purpose.

All presentations or other outputs and publications have the following standard text included at the bottom (or in the acknowledgements for publications):

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research & innovation programme under grant agreement No 953152.

Further dissemination materials, created in English, are presented in detail in the next subsections.

In general, any printing of materials has been kept to a minimum, in line with the UN Sustainable Development Goals. In preference, electronic versions will be distributed where possible, although some printed materials will be required for dissemination during face-to-face conferences, workshops and other events.

Banner/Roll-up

A project roll-up was created to provide an additional aid to communication and dissemination activities. It contains very basic information about the project and is presented in Annex 3.

The banner is visually oriented and its main purpose is to gain audience attention. Its content is clear and easily understandable to all target groups.

Flyer

A project flyer was created (presented in Annex 4) to inform about the DIAGONAL project objectives and expected results. It is used for online communication and dissemination and will also be distributed to the different stakeholder networks at, e.g., thematically relevant

³ <https://www.diagonalproject.eu/downloads/>

conferences. The DIAGONAL flyer is available electronically (as PDF)⁴ and was also printed and distributed to partners during the project.

General Poster

No general poster was created at the beginning of the project due to COVID-19-related travel restrictions. Further in the project, many posters were created by partners containing their specific contributions.

DIAGONAL Stakeholders

DIAGONAL target audiences and general stakeholder groups are (i) research community, (ii) industry, innovation community and industry associations, (iii) standardization and regulatory bodies, and (iv) the general public, civil society organisations and media.

A full evaluation of stakeholders and their corresponding engagement activities is chronicled in Deliverable D2.6 (M42). DIAGONAL has identified the following target groups of stakeholders to which dissemination activities will be directed:

- **Research Community (RC).** A key actor to multiply the dissemination of the project results has been the EU-NanoSafety Cluster (NSC). Beyond Europe, DIAGONAL endeavored to establish communication channels with research communities from other countries active in OECD processes. Here, the EU-US CoRs were targeted. Two US chairs of the Risk Assessment and the Exposure through Product Life CoRs are part of the Advisory Board (Mark R. Wiesner from Duke University and Paul Westerhoff from Arizona State University). In addition, Arno Gutleb (LIST) is also chair of the Human Toxicology CoR. Finally, members of the Thailand National Nanotechnology Center and SUNUM (Sabanci University Nanotechnology Research and Application Center) are part of the Advisory Group. Ineke Malsch of EthicSchool joined as Ethics Advisor.
- **Consultants (C).** This group has been identified within the Lean Canvas of the DIAGONAL SSbD Decision Support Tool (DST) as being one of the primary customer segments for the DST. Specifically, these are consultants with expertise in one or more of the 5 SSbD assessment steps and in the field of nanotechnology. When reaching higher TRLs, experts from the stakeholder matrix (c.f. D7.5) were targeted through further expert interviews, using online marketing and content creation as well as at industry conferences.
- **Industry, innovation community and industry associations (IC).** The nanomaterial / nano-enabled products manufacturers and the downstream industries need to be encouraged to adopt an S(S)bD approach. These target groups, as explained in the 2.1 Expected impact section, will be key to encourage the adoption of the project results by industry, with a special emphasis on SMEs. Networks in which the partners are members include the NANO futures ETTIP, the EU-NSC, the

⁴ <https://www.diagonalproject.eu/diagonal-flyer/>

Nanotechnology Industries Association, SusChem, the EPPN, ETPIS (Technology Platform on Industrial Safety), EIT Raw Materials or the ETP Nanomedicine. Industry was also reached through the consortium connection with associations, OITB projects and specific dissemination and communication activities of the project.

- **Standardisation and Regulatory Bodies (SRB).** The scientific work outputs were translated into specific recommendations for nano-risk governance and standardisation working groups as part of the EU NanoSafety Cluster "Roadmap Safe and Sustainable Advanced and Innovative Materials 2024-2030"⁵. DIAGONAL partners interacted with CEN/CENELEC, ISO, ECHA, DG Research, EFSA and OECD, among others, and these experiences fed into the recommendations provided. Some partners continued active participation in such bodies, like ISQ (secretary in the Portuguese Technical Committee 194 which participates in the work carried out by CEN 352 and ISO 229) or BNN (collaborating in the Austrian Standards Institute Working Group (ASI AG) on "Nanotechnologies & Nanomaterials"; the OECD WPMN; the ISO/TC 229 Nanotechnologies, CEN/TC 352 Nanotechnologies and CEN/TC 137 assessment of workplace exposure to chemical and biological agents; and with ECHA during a bilateral knowledge exchange workshop⁶). In parallel, connection with public institutions was established. The German Federal Institute for Occupational Safety (BAuA) is part of the AB. Additionally, OECD Working Party on Biotechnology, Nanotechnology and Converging Technologies (BNCT) supports the project through a Letter of Interest. Besides, partners as QSAR Lab assisted as national representatives and experts to forums like High Level Group of EU Member States and Horizon 2020 Associated Countries on Nanosciences, Nanotechnologies and Advanced Materials or the OECD Working Groups on safety of nanotechnology.
- **Interest Groups and NGOs (IG).** Non-governmental organizations and interest groups at not only European but also the national levels are important, and their viewpoints need to be heard during the development process of the nano-assessment strategy. Thus we invited the Austrian consumer protection association Verein für Konsumenteninformation (VKI) to our Expert Workshop on Public Perceptions of Nanoparticles in Sunscreens where their representative was able to give ample input.
- **General Public (GP).** Special attention should be paid to the way that scientific research findings are communicated to the general public, especially regarding the improvement of social acceptance and the explanation of the work undertaken by the European Union to grant consumers' safety. Much of this work is supplemented by insights from Task 7.2: Assessment of social sustainability of MCNMs & HARNs. Additionally, DIAGONAL has gathered the support from several organisations and projects (see Figure 5).

5 [https://www.csbj.org/article/S2001-0370\(24\)00161-2/fulltext](https://www.csbj.org/article/S2001-0370(24)00161-2/fulltext)

6 https://issuu.com/bnn-bionanonet/docs/quarterly_0124_6/8

Figure 5. Organizations supporting DIAGONAL.

The specification of relevant stakeholder organizations within each stakeholder group was performed within the exploitation development in a stakeholder matrix (see D7.5) as well as in close collaboration with WP2 (i.e., Task 2.2 on “Liaison management, stakeholder engagement & international cooperation”) within D2.5 and in D2.6 “Report on all performed stakeholder engagement activities”. All stakeholder engagement activities are kept GDPR compliant.

Key messages

Research and innovation outcomes produced along the project will be translated into key messages to be transmitted through the available communication and dissemination channels to the targeted audience groups. The DIAGONAL Consortium described the key messages to be communicated as shown in Table 1.

The main goal of the dissemination plan is to set a strategic approach to exchange knowledge and transfer the project outcomes with the aim to enable others to use and take up results, thus maximising its impact. The dissemination plan is divided in three layers, backing up the development of the R&D activities:

- **Awareness layer (M1 – M18).** Dissemination needs at the first layer involve awareness of the project objectives and expected results addressed to other EU funded projects, universities, institutions, scientific communities, stakeholders and relevant networks, where the required information can be identified and collected. This stage is closely related to the communication activities, as described in the next chapter. In this context, it is crucial to establish the proper working relations with stakeholders and related initiatives.
- **Scientific cooperation (M6 – M42).** The second layer aims to establish the necessary communication channels between the consortium and other stakeholders to facilitate the exchange of information and knowledge transfer. On one hand, it will

enable the management of external information through technical communications, meetings, etc., in order to continue steering the research work of the project. On the other hand, it will enable the transfer of knowledge to the targeted communities (NSC, Malta Initiative, other projects, etc.).

- **Replication and exploitation layer (M36 – M42).** The third layer is highly interlinked with WP7 and the project objective of mainstreaming the tools for its adoption by industry. Also, regulation and standardisation bodies will be tackled to integrate the recommendations and guidelines developed into the governance scenario. This layer will be characterised by strong presence of the project partners in industrial events and workshops, political conferences, but also by dedicated dissemination materials targeted for the industry and the policy framework. [The project's final exploitation roadmap is available in D7.5.](#)

Table 1. Key messages of the project addressing different target groups.

Layer	Key messages	Target group	Key channels & tools
Awareness (M1 – M18)	Project objectives, expected impacts and results	All	Project website, project factsheets, newsletter contributions, social media (LinkedIn and Twitter)
	First results: main knowledge & data gaps on MCNMs/HARNs	RC, SRB	Scientific publications in relevant journals, contributions to scientific events (e.g., presentations at conferences)
Scientific cooperation (M6 – M42)	Modelling approaches, advancements and results	RC, C, IC, SRB	Workshop and/or webinar, scientific publications in relevant journals, workshop and/or webinar, contributions to scientific events (e.g., presentations at conferences)
	Risk assessment and management results and recommendations	RC, IC, SRB	Workshop and/or webinar, scientific publications in relevant journals, contributions to scientific events (e.g., presentations at conferences)
	Risk governance results and recommendations	RC, SRB	Workshop and/or webinar, scientific publications in relevant journals, contributions to scientific events (e.g., presentations at conferences)
Replication & exploitation (M36 – M42)	Best practices, final conclusions, lessons learnt	All	Project website, project factsheets, newsletter contributions, workshop and/or webinar, scientific publications in relevant journals, social media (LinkedIn and twitter)

	Computational and S(S)bD tools	RC, C, IC, SRB	Project website, scientific publications in relevant journals, contributions to scientific events (e.g., presentations at conferences), social media (LinkedIn and twitter), final webinar , video
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Further information about stakeholders and stakeholder engagement activities is chronicled in deliverable “D2.6: Report on all performed stakeholder engagement activities” (M42).

In the final stage of the project, two stakeholder groups were identified that required special attention: SMEs and the general public.

As **SMEs** will be a future target group to benefit from our Key Exploitable Result, the DIAGONAL SSbD Decision Support Tool, we redoubled efforts to reach them. First, BNN in house, in collaboration with BRI and several partners, created an animated video to introduce SSbD and the SSbD Decision Support Tool to people working at SMEs, industry and research organizations. The video intended to attract the interest of people who might not be experts in SSbD but who are interested in learning about methods on how to develop safe and sustainable materials. The video used a conversational tone with simple, direct information, introducing SSbD as a concept and giving an overview of how a user could get the information they needed from the tool. The video is posted on the DIAGONAL YouTube channel⁷ and the DIAGONAL website⁸, and was shared on LinkedIn and Twitter.

In addition, we prepared a set of factsheets – one is dedicated to SMEs (“Short Guide to Nanomaterials for SMEs”), providing some background for SMEs that might not know if they are producing nanoparticles in order to orient themselves. One version of the factsheet also has a QR code linking to the DIAGONAL website and SME survey. (The other 2 factsheets are mentioned under the general public below.)

⁷ <https://youtu.be/GUF3AVTiSHQ?si=wJfcXZ9hcvWJgVZy>

⁸ <https://www.diagonalproject.eu/ssbd-decision-support-tool/>

Figure 6: Factsheet "Short Guide to Nanomaterials for SMEs"

Finally, Graphene-XT, Brimatech and BNN collaborated to prepare a survey to raise awareness among SMEs regarding their (potentially inadvertent) production of nanoparticles and pointing them in the right direction to SSbD tools and methods (while cross-promoting the DIAGONAL SSbD Decision Support Tool).⁹ The survey guides the user step-by-step through the production, application and recycling/disposal stages to help them identify at what point they might be producing nanoparticles. At the end, the user gets a short list of recommendations and is directed toward a resources page newly added to the DIAGONAL website.¹⁰

In parallel, the **general public** was chosen as a group to focus on, to increase awareness of and trust in the SSbD concept, and the more general concepts of nanosafety and nanomaterials. This stakeholder group was addressed in a comprehensive workshop organized with IZES GmbH. The output from this workshop (summarized in D7.2) fed into our

⁹ <https://www.diagonalproject.eu/smes-nano-awareness-survey-start/>

¹⁰ <https://www.diagonalproject.eu/ssbd-resources-for-smes/>

communication strategies and identified further need for basic info on nanomaterials. Thus the team of IZES, Brimatech and BNN decided to create a simple and fun quiz for the public to increase their knowledge of nanomaterials. We also created 2 accompanying fact sheets, which partners were encouraged to take to public science events such as European Researchers' Night.¹¹

How can we design „nano“ to be safe and sustainable?

← 10⁻⁹ Meter = 1 Nanometer 10⁻⁶ Meter = 1 Micrometer 10⁻³ Meter = 1 Millimeter 1 Meter →

Did you know that?

There are 1 billion nano-meters in 1 meter.

A strand of human hair is about 100,000 nm in diameter!

Where do we use nanoparticles & nanomaterials?

- Cosmetics
- Health
- Automotive
- Aerospace
- Oil & Gas
- Textile
- printed electronics

Are nanomaterials safe for humans and the environment?

To determine the risk, we look at hazard x exposure. Hazard means how toxic something is and exposure means how often and how likely it is that you are coming in contact with it. That means that the more you are in contact with a material, the more risk it poses.

So a product used on your skin every day, like a facial cream, has different exposure than a golf ball which you use to play twice a year.

The more you are in contact with a material and the more toxic it is, the more risk it poses.

HAZARD x EXPOSURE = RISK

What do nanoparticles look like?

How do we determine if nanomaterials are safe for humans and the environment?

There is a new approach called Safe-and-Sustainable-by-Design (SSbD). That means looking at safety and sustainability alongside designing a new product.

There are several tools, methods and approaches available for determining safety (e.g. cytotoxicity tests) and sustainability (e.g. life cycle assessments).

The DIAGONAL project is funded by the European Commission to help researchers and companies that develop products containing High-Aspect-Ratio Nanoparticles (HARNs) and Multicomponent nanomaterials (MCNMs) to navigate the tools, methods and approaches available to develop them safely and sustainably, using the Safe-and-Sustainable-by-Design (SSbD) approach.

We have developed the DIAGONAL SSbD Decision Support Tool to help you!

Take our quiz to find out!

Funded by the European Union

DIAGONAL project has received funding from the European Union's HORIZON 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement n° 953152.

Figure 7: Factsheet "How can we design 'nano' to be safe and sustainable?"

¹¹ <https://www.diagonalproject.eu/how-nano-is-the-world-around-you/>

How “nano” is the world around you?

Take our fun quiz to find out!

Discover the fascinating world of nanotechnology!

In which products can you find nanoparticles & nanomaterials?

Cosmetics:

- Nanoparticles in Sunscreen: Zinc oxide or titanium dioxide nanoparticles provide UV protection
- Nanocapsules: Deliver fragrances or other active ingredients in perfumes and creams for extended release

Health:

- Nanoparticle Drug Delivery Systems: Targeted delivery of drugs leads to minimizing side effects
- Silver Nanoparticles: Used in wound dressings and coatings for medical devices due to their antimicrobial properties

Automotive:

- Nanocomposite Materials: Lighter and stronger materials used in car parts, improving fuel efficiency and vehicle safety
- Carbon Nanotubes: Enhance the performance of batteries and other energy storage systems in electric vehicles

Aerospace:

- Nanocoatings: Improve thermal insulation, corrosion resistance, and wear resistance of aerospace components
- Nanomaterials in Sensors: Enhance the sensitivity and accuracy of sensors used in navigation and monitoring systems

Oil & Gas:

- Nanofluids: Improve the efficiency of drilling and extraction processes by enhancing heat transfer and reducing friction
- Nanoparticle-based Catalysts: Increase the efficiency of refining processes and reduce energy consumption

Textiles:

- Nanofibers: Used in the production of high-performance fabrics with enhanced strength, breathability, and comfort
- Nanosilver: Provides antimicrobial and odor-resistant properties in clothing and sportswear

Printed Electronics:

- Conductive Inks: Contain nanoparticles of silver, copper, or carbon nanotubes, used in flexible and wearable electronic devices
- Organic Light Emitting Diodes (OLEDs): Employ nanoscale materials to produce thin, flexible, and efficient display screens
- Nanocapsules: Deliver fragrances or other active ingredients in perfumes and creams for extended release

The DIAGONAL project is funded by the European Commission to help those who develop products containing High-Aspect-Ratio Nanoparticles (HARNs) and Multicomponent nanomaterials (MCNMs) to navigate the tools and methods available to use them safely and sustainably, using the Safe-and-Sustainable-by-Design (SSbD) approach.

Are you using nanomaterials?
The DIAGONAL SSbD Decision Support Tool can help you!
diagonalproject.eu

Funded by the European Union

DIAGONAL project has received funding from the European Union's HORIZON 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement n° 953152.

Figure 8: Factsheet on applications of nanomaterials

Communication & Dissemination Strategy

A strategically planned communication process started with the project kick-off and will continue throughout its entire lifetime. All subtopics that are contributing to the overall DIAGONAL communication and dissemination strategy are described in detail on the next pages.

Internal Communication & Overall Project Cooperation

DIAGONAL's success depends on an open and clear communication between all participants ensuring each participant is kept up-to-date on work progress, next steps, outcomes of meetings and task allocation.

The project coordinator and the project management team offer administrative support for all partners: support in administrative matters, including the preparation of reports, host web-conferences, organisation of meetings, keep addresses, send reminders for dates and events, organize documentation, provide individual templates for reports and financial statements, provide training on administrative procedures and streamline the reporting.

File Exchange and Data Storage

The project coordination team has created a restricted-access/password protected area for internal documentation and exchange of information using a protected project file server.

This file server is employed for storing confidential documents, data and information. The documents are organised by an appropriate structure, set up by the project coordinator. It contains all documentation (Grant Agreement, Consortium Agreement and all EC communications), contact details of all participants, project logo and templates, project meeting information (agenda, minutes, presentations), final versions of deliverables and milestones, activity reports, monitoring reports, dissemination documentation, marketing material, etc.

The file server is managed by UBU, all project partners can upload and access documents and information.

Email/Telephone

In addition to the project's file server and face-to-face meetings (COVID-19 permitting), the Consortium will use additional communication channels to enhance teamwork between physical meetings and maintain open and transparent communication: e-mails and phone calls for regular and daily communication and (video) conferences (e.g., via MS Teams, GoToMeeting or others).

Reporting

The status-quo of the internal communication is reflected in the reporting activities of the project. There are mainly two different official paths for sharing progress information between the partners and the EC: deliverables and periodic reports, both described in detail in the following subsections.

Deliverables

The list of deliverables is described in the section 1.3.2 – “WT2 List of deliverables” of the Annex 1 (Part A) of the Grant Agreement (GA), pages 6-11. Within DIAGONAL there is an internal review process of deliverables. Once all relevant partners have given their feedback for the concrete deliverable, it will be sent for internal review to the WP leader and to the project coordination team. After finalization of the deliverable, it will be uploaded to the participant portal by the project coordinator. Public deliverables are also added to the DIAGONAL website under the Publications page.

Periodic Reports / Final Report

As required by Article 20 of the GA, a report summarizing scientific progress, management and financial issues will be submitted to the EC after months 19, 33 and 43. Hence, all partners will submit reports to the project coordinator strictly in accordance with the guidelines and rules provided by the EC. The coordinator will verify these reports and submit them to the EC via the SYGMA system in the Participant Portal.

Meetings

Tables 2 and 3 show the DIAGONAL meeting plan, with regular meetings planned for monitoring the performance of the project.

Table 2. Project meeting plan.

Month (Project Runtime)	Date	Type of Meeting	Location
M1	4 & 12 May 2021	Kick-Off Meeting	Virtual
M9	12-13 January 2022	General Assembly	Virtual
M14	24 June 2022	General Assembly	Limassol (CY)
M18	15 December 2022	Review Meeting	Virtual
M24	17 May 2023	General Assembly	Burgos (ES)
M34	27 Feb 2024	2 nd Review Meeting	Virtual
M38	6 June 2024	General Assembly	Virtual
M41	26 Sept 2024	General Assembly	Venice (IT)

M42+2	16 December 2024	Final Review Meeting	Virtual
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Table 3. List of regular meetings.

Frequency	Type of Meeting	Location
Every 6 months	General Assembly	Virtual / f2f (if possible, at least once per year)
All three months	S&TC regular meetings	Virtual
(Bi-)Monthly	WP regular meetings	Virtual
As necessary	Ad hoc meetings, for urgent issues	Virtual
As necessary	Project Coordinator / DIAGONAL Project Advisor	Virtual / f2f

Additional meetings were held, for example, to discuss exploitation, IP issues, dissemination activities and other issues in the consortium.

External Communication & Dissemination

All DIAGONAL partners will communicate and disseminate relevant project results to the relevant audiences by appropriate means unless there are unresolved issues with intellectual property rights (IPR). WP7 manages all communication and dissemination efforts, and has an obligation to protect IPR of project outcomes. Each project partner aspires to use open access for all peer-reviewed scientific publications describing their results in line, with provisions of Article 29 and 38 of the Grant Agreement. [More information on the IPR strategy is available in D7.4.](#)

To develop an efficient Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Strategy for the project and create successful and targeted action plans, we begin by describing the concepts of and differences between communication, dissemination and exploitation, summarized in Table 4.

Table 4. Concepts of Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation.¹²

	Communication	Dissemination	Exploitation
Definition ¹³	Communication on projects is a strategically planned process that starts at the outset of the action and continues throughout its entire lifetime, aimed at promoting the action and its results. It requires strategic and targeted measures for communicating about (i) the action and (ii) its results to a multitude of audiences, including the media and the public and possibly engaging in a two-way exchange.	The public disclosure of project results by any appropriate means (other than resulting from protecting or exploiting the results), including scientific publications, videos and any other medium.	The utilization of results in further research activities other than those covered by the action concerned, or in developing, creating and marketing a product or process, or in creating and providing a service, or in standardization activities.
Objectives	Reach out to society and show the impact and benefits of EU-funded R&I activities, e.g., by addressing and providing possible solutions to fundamental societal challenges.	Transfer knowledge & results with the aim to enable others to use and take up results, thus maximizing the impact of EU-funded research. Covers project results only .	Effectively use project results through scientific, economic, political or societal exploitation routes aiming to turn R&I actions into

¹² <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/3bb7278e-ebf3-11e9-9c4e-01aa75ed71a1/language-en>

¹³ EC Research & Innovation Participant Portal Glossary, Reference Terms. <https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/support/glossary>

			concrete value and impact for society.
When	Starts at the outset of the project .	Happens only once results are available.	Happens only once results, services or products are available.
Focus	Inform about and promote the project AND its results/success → Focus on the whole project (including results).	Describe and ensure results available for others to use → Focus on results only .	Make concrete use of research results (not restricted to commercial use)
Target Audience	Multiple audiences beyond the project's own community, including the media and general public. Multiplier effect.	Specialist audiences - Groups that may use the results in their own work, including peer groups, industry, professional organisations, policy-makers.	People/organizations including project partners themselves that make concrete use of the project results, as well as user groups outside the project.
Formal Obligations	Legal reference GA Article 38.1	Legal reference GA Article 29	Legal reference GA Article 28

Table 5 builds a key document of the PEDR as it summarizes the overall communication and dissemination aims of the project. All actions have been allocated to communication media and provided with appropriate resources (time and money). The impact of these activities will be measured by Key Performance Indicators (KPI) which may lead to a re-planning of the strategy followed. The project performance towards the envisaged KPIs will be monitored in M18, M32 and M42, to ensure timely and appropriate corrective measures if needed.

In the following table, **green** refers to targets achieved. **Orange** indicated changes made to targets (e.g. trade fairs target lowered due to decreased interest in trade fairs considering the pandemic and the lower TRL of the current version of the DIAGONAL SSbD DST).

For a detailed list of activities carried out **in the project**, please see the Communications & Dissemination log, found as an annex in the technical report.

Table 5. DIAGONAL planned communication and dissemination activities including evaluation via KPIs.

Project outcome, Timing, Leader	Activity/Specification	Target Group(s)	Measurements, KPIs	Target No. until project end	Evaluation M18	Evaluation M32	Evaluation M42
Communication Toolkit & Dissemination Pack Project roll-up, flyer(s), general poster, etc. (M4 until end of project / Budget reserved for printing, content/design by WP7 / BNN)	Provide online and/or printed project information for communication & dissemination activities, e.g., at events such as conferences, meetings and science hotspots.	All	Google-based analysis • # of downloaded copies • # of printed copies • # of distributed copies	• 100 downloaded flyer/poster • 300 printed flyers (if needed) • 300 distributed flyer (if printed)	• 69 downloads • 250 printed flyers • 100 distributed flyers	• 142 downloads • 500 printed flyers • 250 distributed flyers	• 142 downloads • 500 printed flyers • 500 distributed flyers
Website (M4 until the end of project / Budget reserved for technical implementation, content design and updates by WP7 / BNN)	Provides easy access to project information; Core of external communication & dissemination activities to all (public) stakeholders.	All	Google analytics • # of website users • # of website sessions	• 3,500 website users	• 1,074 users • 1,546 sessions	• 2,323 users • 3,124 sessions	• 5,098 users • 6,697 sessions
Social media (M1 with increase towards the 2 nd half of the project / Postings)	Addressing defined international target groups via Twitter and LinkedIn.	All	Twitter statistics, LinkedIn analytics • # of followers • # of postings	• Twitter: 100-150 followers, >20,000 impressions	• 93 Twitter followers; 10,988 impressions	• 119 Twitter followers; 16,280 impressions	• 167 Twitter followers; 18,227 impressions

implemented by WP7 / BNN)			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • # of impressions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • LinkedIn: 150-200 followers, >25.000 impressions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 205 LinkedIn followers; 23,379 impressions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 263 LinkedIn followers; 41,434 impressions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 351 LinkedIn followers; 57,811 impressions
<p>Newsletter (M1 until end of the project; at least two newsletter contributions per year, coordinated within WP7 / BNN)</p>	Increase the project's visibility to all stakeholders by making use of already established newsletters, e.g., BNN NEWSLETTER, EU NSC newsletter, etc.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • RC • IC • SRB • IG 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • # of newsletter contributions released • # of newsletter reach/receivers • # of newsletter views • # of newsletter downloads 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 7 newsletter contributions released • 500 newsletter views 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 6 newsletter contributions • 2056 newsletter views 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 12 newsletter contributions • 5349 newsletter views 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 18 newsletter contributions • 10874 newsletter views
<p>Press Releases (M1 until end of the project; at all major results / Press departments of participants, tracking by WP7 / UBU)</p>	Professionally compiled information about the project/results for distribution in (partner's) newsletters and basis for science journalists.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • All 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • # of press releases • # of views on the website & social media 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 2 press releases • 50 website views; 1000 social media impressions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 2 press releases • 33 website views; 791 social media impressions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 3 press releases • 33 website views; 791 social media impressions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 3 press releases • 33 website views; 791 social media impressions
<p>Scientific Publications (M1 with increasing effort towards the 2nd half of the project / Publication fees as budgeted by</p>	Add scientific credibility to results by publishing in peer reviewed journals and open research platforms, respecting the H2020 obligation for open access publishing.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • RC • SRB • IC 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • # of publications • Journal's impact factor • # of citations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 20 scientific publications published 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 6 scientific publications • 5.253 average journal impact factor • 0 citations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 18 scientific publications • 7.119 average journal impact factor • 16 citations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 20 scientific publications • 7.84 average journal impact factor • 79 citations

each partner / All partners)							
<p>Project Fact Sheets</p> <p>(M12 until end of project / Budget reserved for printing, content/design by WP7 / UBU & BNN)</p>	<p>Providing online and/or printed project information for dissemination activities such as conferences, meetings and science hotspots.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • RC • SRB • IC 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • # of downloaded copies • # of printed copies • # of distributed copies 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 50 downloaded copies 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Not yet made 	<p>Not yet made</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 74 downloaded copies • 50 printed copies
<p>DIAGONAL Workshops & Training Activities</p> <p>(M1 with an increase towards the 2nd half of the project / Content provided by all technical WPs / All partners)</p>	<p>Workshops aim (i) to establish scientific cooperation with targeted research projects & initiatives and to disseminate project results on RA, RM and RG; (ii) to disseminate the project results among targeted industrial stakeholders towards the end of the project.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • RC • SRB • IC 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • # of workshops/trainings • # of training materials produced • # of participants • Evaluation of feedback of participants 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 4 workshops held • >25 workshop participants 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 2 workshops held 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 4 workshops held 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 5 workshops/trainings held • 2 training materials produced¹⁴ • 200 participants

14 Results from the TRAAC workshops were integrated into D7.5 and could be used by the DST developers to understand the most common issues and drawbacks.

<p>DIAGONAL Webinars & Knowledge Transfer: (M1 with an increase towards the 2nd half of the project / Content provided by all technical WPs / All partners)</p>	<p>Webinars aim (i) to establish scientific cooperation with targeted research projects & initiatives and to disseminate project results on RA, RM and RG; (ii) to disseminate the project results among targeted industrial stakeholders towards the end of the project.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • RC • SRB • IC 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • # of webinars • # of participants • # of recordings produced • Evaluation of feedback of participants 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 4 webinars held • >25 webinar participants 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 0 webinars held 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 1 webinars held 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 3 webinars held • >40 webinar participants
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<p>Scientific Conferences attended by DIAGONAL (M1 until project end / Participation coordinated by WP2 & monitored by WP7 / All partners)</p>	<p>Expand the knowledge gained through the project.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • RC • IC • SRB • IG 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • # of conferences attended 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 20 conferences attended 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 8 conferences attended 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 29 conferences attended 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 39 conferences attended
<p>Trade Fairs (M1 until project end / Participation coordinated by WP7 / All partners)</p>	<p>Increase engagement with industries at targeted trade fairs.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • IC 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • # of trade fairs attended 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 2 trade fairs attended 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 0 trade fairs attended 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 0 trade fairs attended 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 0 trade fairs attended

<p>Meetings with standardization bodies (M1 until project end / Coordinated by WP2 & WP6 / All partners)</p>	<p>Directed to contribute to the OECD Malta Initiative, REACH reviews and future R&D roadmaps.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SRB • RC 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • #of meetings attended 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 4 meetings attended 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 1 meeting attended 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 2 meetings attended 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 3 meetings attended
<p>Reports and deliverables (M1 until project end, monitored by the project coordination team in WP1 / UBU)</p>	<p>According to the requirements of the EC, demonstrating the project’s progress</p>	<p>Project partners</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reports/Deliverables on the EC participant portal 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 53 Deliverables submitted • 12 Milestones achieved 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 12 deliverables submitted • 3 milestones achieved 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 28 deliverables submitted • 8 milestones achieved 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 40 deliverables submitted¹⁵ • 9 milestones achieved

The table shows that almost all KPIs were achieved in the project. The following were not achieved, with a short explanation where applicable:

Twitter impressions (Target: 20,000; Actual achieved: 18,227) At the start of the project several partners were very active on Twitter. However, as the project continued and many changes on the platform (renamed “X”) were carried out, the platform became less attractive, especially for those in the research space. Therefore a few partners stopped using Twitter/X and overall the impressions per post declined. Discussions moved to LinkedIn during this time, and we saw more impressions on that platform.

Press release (Target: 50 website views; 1000 social media impressions; Actual achieved: 33 website views; 791 social media impressions) The press releases were at the beginning of the project before a large following was established. As the Key Exploitable Result, the DST, was not ready to officially launch, it was decided to “soft launch” with a series of activities such as the DST video, a subpage on the website, the final dissemination event in Venice and the informational webinar. Combined views of these activities are well above the target threshold.

As previously mentioned, the target for trade fairs was removed due to the lower TRL of the Decision Support Tool.

¹⁵ As of submission of this deliverable in mid-October. Remaining deliverables and milestones due Oct 31st are not counted.

Training materials were not produced per se, but results from the 2 TRAAC workshops were integrated into the D7.5 and can be used for the DIAGONAL developers to see what are the most common issues and drawbacks.

Webinars lost their appeal by the time DIAGONAL was getting underway and the pandemic was abating, so we only held 3 webinars in the project. Instead, we were able to attend many more conferences and in-person events than expected at the beginning. In addition, our DST explanatory video was created in place of a webinar at the time.

Three meetings with standardization bodies were held – one with the OECD and one as a bilateral training between ECHA and DIAGONAL partner BNN.

Although BNN coordinates the communication and dissemination activities, all DIAGONAL project partners are expected to actively participate in activities. To monitor them, a template “DIAGONAL_WP7_Comm&Diss_Log.xlsx” (presented in Annex 5) was created by BNN and shared with all partners on the shared file server. The categories to choose as type of communication and dissemination activity are based on the periodic reporting required in the EC Participants’ Portal.

The following information will be reported by all partners:

- Project runtime (month xx)
- Date/time period (dd.mm.yyyy)
- Partner (Acronym) (lead partner in bold)
- Location/Repository
- Communication & Dissemination Activity:
 - Project Meeting
 - Organisation of a conference
 - Organisation of a workshop
 - Press release
 - Non-scientific and non-peer reviewed publications (popularised publications)
 - Exhibition
 - Flyer
 - Training
 - Social media
 - Website
 - Communication campaign (e.g., radio, TV)
 - Participation to a conference
 - Participation to a workshop
 - Participation to an event other than a conference or workshop
 - Video / Film
 - Brokerage event
 - Pitch event
 - Trade fair
 - Participation in activities organised jointly with other H2020 project(s)
 - Other
- Title of event/newsletter etc.
- Content/Brief description/Presentation title etc.
- No. of persons reached (e.g., participants, prints, views, etc.)
- Type of audience addressed:
 - Scientific community (higher education, research)
 - Industry
 - Civil society
 - General public
 - Policy makers
 - Media
 - Investors
 - Customers

- Other
- External link to activity (if relevant)
- Link to news/event at DIAGONAL webpage
- Countries addressed
- Comments

A different template is used to monitor the publications specifically, also based on the form at the EC Participants' Portal:

- Type
 - Article in Journal
 - Publication in conference proceedings/workshop
 - Book/Monograph
 - Chapter in a book
 - Thesis/Dissertation
 - Other
- Title
- Author(s)
- Title of Journal/Proceedings/Books series/Book (for book chapters)
- Year
- Page reference
- DOI
- Repository link
- Open Access Status (Green/Gold)
- Comments

Several activities are planned to engage with relevant stakeholders. These activities will be potentially merged with sister projects' activities or conferences to better interact with the relevant stakeholders and to join efforts with other ongoing activities, reaching a wider community, thus saving and aligning resources. The liaison management with other (NMBP) projects is performed in WP2 and thus closely linked with Task 2.2 and Task 2.3.

All communication and dissemination activities comply with the GDPR and are aligned with the privacy policy of the project.

All relevant-for-the-community communication and dissemination activities will be reported on the website and/or social media channels of the project.

DIAGONAL has organized workshops/webinars/events/etc. to engage with the different stakeholder groups. Registration forms allow the participants to sign-up for these activities/events organized by the project. Personal information (e.g., name, email-address, affiliation, etc.) collected for such events will be accompanied by relevant permissions and details of how personal data will be handled (i.e., used, stored and destroyed). This data is not shared with third parties. Registration and participant lists are kept electronically on a secure server. Physical signature lists of attendees at face-to-face meetings, such as Consortium Meetings, are kept in a secure cabinet. The webinars and workshops and other online events organized by DIAGONAL may be recorded for training purposes. Therefore, permissions will be requested from participants prior to the start of the meetings. In any case,

only relevant data will be kept and processed during the project and will be limited to the purposes of DIAGONAL, in accordance with the 'data minimization principle'.

In addition, attendance to conferences through active participation and sending of abstracts will be promoted within the project. Additionally, all the partners will continuously identify and interact with national and local events of interest as appropriate.

Conferences and events

To disseminate our results, the DIAGONAL partners organized or co-organized 4 conferences and 1 event. Most of these events were organized with NMBP-16 sister projects and NMBP-15 projects, to maximize synergies between the projects and share best practices.

In June 2022 in Limassol, Cyprus, DIAGONAL supported organization of NanoWeek 2022 and was represented with 1 oral presentation and 2 poster presentations. It was the first in-person conference/meeting since the pandemic and coincided with a project consortium meeting and the NMBP-16 Ambassadors meeting.

One day after a DIAGONAL General Assembly, ICCRAM/UBU held a conference "Safe and sustainable by design strategies towards innovation" in Burgos, with 3 oral presentations from DIAGONAL partners LIST, DTI and Monolithos.

Initiated by BNN, DIAGONAL was part of the organizers and sponsors of ANTHOS'24, which took place 4-7 March 2024 in Vienna. Short for "Advanced (Nano)Materials and Technologies: Science, Research & Innovation for Safety and Sustainability", ANTHOS was a collaboration of NMBP-15 and-16 projects, with an oral presentation and roundtable discussion with DIAGONAL coordinator Carlos Rumbo (ICCRAM), a public engagement workshop from IZES, and participation from OcSiAL, CreativeNano, and ITENE. The conference passed down lessons learned from NMBP-15 projects to NMBP-16 projects and allowed for in-depth and critical discussions of the impacts of our Key Exploitable Results.

From 23-25 September 2024 DIAGONAL partners organized NanoTox 2024 (the 11th International Conference on NanoToxicology) in Venice. NanoTox focuses on the challenges related to safe and sustainable multicomponent nanomaterials by developing novel tools for evaluating human and environmental hazards, strategies for nanomaterial characterisation, classification, grouping and read-across for risk analysis and sustainability assessment. By organizing it jointly with other projects we were able to attract 230 visitors from industry, academia and policy sectors. Here DIAGONAL was heavily involved with representatives chairing sessions, presenting oral presentations and posters, and exhibiting a booth.

A joint final dissemination event on 25 September 2024 in Venice with the NMBP-16 projects HARMLESS and SUNSHINE attracted 50 people in person to learn about the legacies of the projects and specific KERs.

In addition, DIAGONAL partners disseminated results at 39 conferences with oral presentations and posters, including in the United States. For a full list, see the Communication & Dissemination log in the Annex.

Social Media in the Project

Social media will help to reach a wide, but targeted audience, maximizing impact and successful exploitation of the DIAGONAL results. The project will continuously post content about project relevant issues. In WP7, content generation will be coordinated by requesting all project beneficiaries to provide content.

Table 6 summarizes the characteristics of the two popular social media networks that are used by the project, X (formerly Twitter¹⁶) & LinkedIn¹⁷. The posts provide updates on DIAGONAL news, events and any information useful for project promotion to stakeholders. The main aim of using social media is to increase and retain the interest of multiple audiences and to engage new ones. Twitter and LinkedIn will be also used to amplify the content generated in the project webpage. To encourage all partners to share social media content, there will be reminders at all meetings of WP7.

Table 6. Overview of the characteristics of the two social media platforms used in the project.

Platform	Description – What is it and how can it be used?
<p>Twitter (X)</p>	<p>Twitter, now renamed "X," is a public forum where anyone can write and share short messages called 'Tweets'. Twitter members can broadcast tweets and follow other users to receive their tweets.</p> <p>280-character messages including links (a URL is always altered to 23 characters). This excludes media attachments (photos, images, videos, etc.) and quoted tweets (displaying someone else`s tweet within your own).</p> <p>Sharing short comments, announcements that can instantaneously reach a large audience or retweeting relevant content.</p>

¹⁶ <https://twitter.com/DIAGONALproject>

¹⁷ <https://www.linkedin.com/company/diagonalproject>

<p>LinkedIn</p>	<p>LinkedIn is the world's largest professional network on the internet. It can be used to find the right job or internship, connect and strengthen professional relationships. LinkedIn can be accessed from a desktop, LinkedIn mobile app, mobile web experience, or the LinkedIn Lite Android mobile app.</p> <p>A complete LinkedIn profile can help to connect with opportunities by showcasing the project's unique professional story through experience, skills, and education.</p> <p>Also, LinkedIn can be used to organize offline events, join groups, write articles, post photos and videos, and more.</p>
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Social Media Target Audience

The targeted **social media audience**, i.e., those who follow and who to invite others to follow the DIAGONAL profiles, are people who are likely to be interested in the project. We identified three main types of audience: (i) lay people (no special expert knowledge, i.e., general public); (ii) managerial people (may have more knowledge than the lay audience about the subject); (iii) experts (most demanding audience in terms of knowledge). DIAGONAL target audiences are (i) the scientific community, (ii) large industry, SMEs and innovators, (iii) state agencies, regulators, policy makers, and (iv) the general public, civil society organisations and media. After the project was underway, we were able to tailor postings to different audiences using hashtags, tagging relevant organizations and individuals, and modifying language.

Social Media Strategy

The social media strategy aims to:

- Identify and engage people and organizations active in fields related to project activities;
- Increase recognition of the project through social media;
- Spread news and other content about the project such as research articles, public deliverables, marketing material, project content, activities, news, results, etc.;
- Engage social media followers; and
- Create interactive forums at an international level.

The project communicates continuously throughout its lifetime by:

- Launching posts;
- Releasing news items that feature DIAGONAL research & outcomes;
- Publishing videos of lab tours or promotional videos about KERS (e.g. SSbD DST video)
- Linking to any newsletter articles / blog posts DIAGONAL produced;
- Promoting conferences DIAGONAL will be represented at (interesting oral talks, posters, discussions, etc.);
- Inviting followers for dedicated feedback via polls or surveys (e.g. [the Nano-Awareness Survey for SMEs](#) or our public-focused "How nano is the world around you?" survey)
- Publishing interesting news items within the scope of the project;
- Publishing interesting images related to the project topics;

- Reporting new publications or resources (e.g. our factsheets) produced by the project;
- Replying to relevant tweets by other people;
- Retweeting relevant tweets of other people, projects and organizations;
- Promoting project partner organisations and their staff;
- Presenting WPs and their progress;
- Any other useful information.

Some social media activities are pre-planned to maintain regular posts in between periods with no special news.

Publications

DIAGONAL aims to create 20 scientific publications along its runtime. Some partners have already depicted the journals where to publish their peer-reviewed articles: *Environmental Science and Technology*, *Cell Systems*, *Green Chemistry*, *Nature Nanotechnology*, *Journal of Nanobiotechnology*, *International Journal of Hygiene and Environmental Health*, *Environmental Science: Nano*, *NanoImpact*, *Spectroscopic journals*, *BMC Systems Biology*, *International Journal of Life Cycle Assessment*. BNN together with the DIAGONAL coordination team coordinates and monitors the progress from all partners on that topic. As of M32 the consortium has published 10 peer-reviewed articles in scientific journals. As of M42 the consortium had doubled that number, publishing 20 peer-reviewed articles in scientific journals. A further 3 articles have been accepted and 6 articles are in progress as of submission of this deliverable.

Partners have been encouraged to publish joint papers where possible. In addition, five of the published articles were written jointly with other NMBP-16 sister projects (HARMLESS and SUNSHINE).

The publication strategy was periodically discussed during consortium and at S&TC meetings.

Contractual Framework for Publications

Partners will disseminate project results to the public, including via scientific publications.

The following paragraphs of the GA specify communication and dissemination obligations:

- Article 29 – Dissemination of results – Open Access – Visibility of EU funding (pages 49-50 of the GA); and,
- Article 38 – Promoting the action – Visibility of EU funding (pages 57-59 of the GA).

Project partners are committed to Open Access publication as far as possible – the preferred option is Gold Open Access, but self-archiving via Green Open Access is also encouraged.

Internal Procedure for Publications

As required by Article 29 of the GA, if a beneficiary intends to disseminate results, it must give at least 45 days advance notice to the other beneficiaries and sufficient information on the results that will be disseminated. Objections to publication must be received within 30 days

of receiving the notification of intention to disseminate. Further details on how to deal with objections are agreed upon in the CA. A dedicated publication protocol ensures this process is followed. Partners are required to indicate whether they approve the publication, approve with comments, or deny it. These responses are collected through a questionnaire and stored in the DIAGONAL Teams repository.

All disseminated materials from DIAGONAL are available for download through the project's website. All outcomes are assigned a DOI and be published under a Creative Commons License for re-use. If they are not already in a repository then they are added to the DIAOGNAL Zenodo community. Peer-reviewed publications will be made available based on journal requirements.

The European Commission has lately launched the Open Research Europe¹⁸. As an open access publisher, it could have been used for publishing project outcomes of DIAGONAL. However, so far partners have submitted manuscripts to peer-reviewed journals in first place.

Completed Communication & Dissemination Activities

Main DIAGONAL activities (dissemination material, events, workshops, newsletters, etc.) are announced in the "News" section of the project website¹⁹ as well as in the social media channels of the project (LinkedIn & Twitter).

Furthermore, all activities by all partners are compiled and regularly updated using the "DIAGONAL_WP7_Comm&Diss_Log.xlsx" (Annex 1).

¹⁸ <https://open-research-europe.ec.europa.eu/>

¹⁹ <https://www.diagonalproject.eu/news/>

Exploitation Plan

The Horizon 2020 program defines 'Exploitation'²⁰ as the "utilization of results in further research activities other than those covered by the action concerned, or in developing, creating and marketing a product or process, or in creating and providing a service or in standardisation activities". Exploitation is about making use of the results; but before exploiting, an exploitation planning is needed for recognizing the exploitable results and their stakeholders. Exploitation can be commercial, societal, political, or for improving public knowledge and action. Project partners can aim at exploiting the project results themselves or facilitate exploitation by others. Furthermore, exploitation concretizes the value and impact of the R&D&I activity for societal challenges.

The exploitation strategy is mainly addressed in Deliverable 7.5, "Exploitation roadmap", due in M42. The Exploitation Plan has the objective to define the strategy to multiply the impact of the proposed solutions and innovations of the DIAGONAL project, to be prepared for the transition towards industrial and commercial uptake in order to fully achieve the expected impacts. The Exploitation Plan describes the activities to be undertaken (how and by whom) in order to ensure the exploitation beyond the project itself.

Overall objectives of the exploitation task (T7.3 Economic sustainability and exploitation, starting in M16) are fostering exploitation by ensuring contacts to stakeholders, collecting needs & requirements, identifying challenges for implementation, summarizing impact, and to further developing the exploitation plan and establishing the exploitation strategy based on the results from WP2, 3, 4, 5 and 6.

Key approaches and tools to identify exploitation paths beyond the project comprise:

- A **target outcomes table of key exploitable results** describes the features of the method / material / product / service that are the outcome of the project.
- A **Stakeholder Matrix** has become the standard tool for giving a comprehensive picture of the community of researchers, potential users, buyers and influencers in an application field. The exploitation target groups are subsets of the dissemination target groups (identified in T2.3) and will be continuously specified in greater detail during the project,
- The initial SSbD **Value Chain** established in T2.4 will be continuously updated in dependence of new project results generated.
- **Selection of the most promising demonstrators** in T7.1 "Cases for sustainability by design" based on predefined KPIs obtained from the brief market analyses in T2.4 "Identification of SMEs needs and market analysis", T7.2 "Assessment of social sustainability of MCNMs & HARNs", KPIs for risk management from WP6 as well as relevant SDGs and environmental KPIs from Task 5.2 "Life Cycle Sustainability concept integration".

²⁰ https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/other/events/2017-03-01/8_result-dissemination-exploitation.pdf

- Follow-up on the brief market analysis for each demonstrator (T2.4) with an **in-depth analysis** to give a more comprehensive insight into SMEs from the nanotechnology industry and their corresponding stakeholders.
- **Lean Canvas Business Planning** for the KER – the DIAGONAL SSbD DST – focusing on the sectors of the most promising 3 demonstrators selected in T7.1
- **Identification of exploitation options**, such as further research activities, development of standards, licensing, or assignment.
- **Identification of funding options** for the further development of the DIAGONAL SSbD DST at dedicated events as well as based on database research.
- Identification of critical IPR issues and development of an **IPR strategy** for the DIAGONAL SSbD DST and its elements.

In order to gather content for the DIAGONAL exploitation strategy and the related exploitation activities, information needs to be collected from various stakeholder groups along the value chain and via different methodological approaches. The main activities for the development of the exploitation strategy comprise:

- Interviews with different stakeholder groups (project internal and external) in person or via phone/internet
- Organization of and participation in exploitation-related workshops
- Attending conferences
- Supporting activities related to the further use of IP generated in DIAGONAL
- Identification of further research areas and promising industry sectors

The International Project Advisory Board and project partners help establish contacts to project external experts and stakeholders.

All the above-mentioned activities will ultimately contribute to the exploitation of the project results beyond the project end and concretize the value and impact of the R&D&I activity for societal challenges. The final exploitation roadmap is available in D7.5.

Exploitation activities and results have been communicated and disseminated in T7.4.

Conclusion

This PEDR provides DIAGONAL with a solid framework for communicating, disseminating and exploiting project results and activities. The DIAGONAL Consortium uses this document as a strategy that has been further revised and updated as dissemination materials and specific strategies were evaluated to reach effectiveness in targeting stakeholders and in aligning with stakeholder interests and problems. *Exploitation efforts became more specific as the project progressed, leading to several workshops, a video and final activities performed with partners and external contacts.*

The PEDR captures and schedules all communication and dissemination activities of the project that support engagement of new stakeholders and increase public awareness of the project and its outcomes. It will assist the project partners by defining communication goals, objectives and strategies by outlining specific dissemination events in which to participate and dissemination activities to perform.

As leader of Task 7.4, BNN continuously monitored and coordinated communication and dissemination activities. WP7 leader BRI ensured appropriate innovation management and developed exploitation strategies in close collaboration and knowledge exchange with the DIAGONAL Consortium. In addition, BNN aligned within WP2 stakeholder engagement activities. All project partners were encouraged to perform further outreach activities and spread the word about the DIAGONAL's progress and results in their communities and at relevant conferences.

In conclusion, the DIAGONAL PEDR employs diverse communication channels, ranging from a project website and social media accounts, etc., through to participation in events (conferences, workshops, meetings, events, joint activities with relevant EU projects, etc.) to maximise internal communications and external interactions with stakeholders. *A final evaluation of the Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation activities will be performed in the final technical report. However, we have ample evidence that the PEDR helped bring DIAGONAL results closer to the scientific community, industry and the public and has brought us closer to relevant exploitation opportunities.*

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https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/other/grants_manual/amga/soc-med-guide_en.pdf

Annex 1: DIAGONAL Communication and Dissemination Log

Communication & Dissemination Activity Log

List of Communication & Dissemination activities, including conferences, workshops, non-scientific publications, that have been done for the project, in chronological order.

Start Date (dd.mm.yyy y)	End date (dd.mm.yyy y)	Partner (Acronym) (lead partner in bold) and main contact person	Location (or Online)	Comm. & Diss. Activity (select from drop-down list)	Title	Content/ Brief description/Purpose	Estimated Number of Attendees								Comments	Link to activity (if relevant)	
							Scientific community (higher education, research)	Industry	Civil society	General public	Policy makers	Media	Investors	Customers			Other
01.06.2021	31.10.2022	BNN (Caitlin Ahern)	Online	Social media	DIAGONAL LinkedIn	Audience for LinkedIn posts (12729 unique impressions)	6365	2545	100	636	536	600	36	72	1200		https://www.facebook.com/iccrsam.ubu/posts/2873949786754478
01.06.2021	31.10.2022	BNN (Caitlin Ahern)	Online	Social media	DIAGONAL Twitter	Audience for Twitter posts (1782 - highest impressions per month)	891	356	10	89	79	89	89	9	170		
20.06.2021		QSAR Lab	Online	Website	Webpage about project Diagonal	About Diagonal, main information	0	0	0	4000	0	0	0	0	0		https://www.qsarlab.com/en/projects/
21.06.2021		BNN (Susanne Resch)	Online	Non-scientific and non-peer reviewed publications (popularised publications)	BNN Newsletter	Article featuring DIAGONAL in newsletter (Project introduction)	193	77	0	19	20	20	19	0	39		https://www.facebook.com/iccrsam.ubu/posts/2904359199880153
22.06.2021	22.06.2021	ICCRAM	Online	Video / Film	Centro de Investigación ICCRAM - Hacia el desarrollo de nuevos materiales	Mention within an institutional video	10	10	10	270	10	7	10	10	10	80 registered people. 347 views. Published on ICCRAM TW,FB,LI	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=bedf5BrEonY
22.06.2021	24.06.2021	BNN (Andreas Falk)	Online	Participation to an event other than a	OECD Meeting - 21st meeting of WPMN		80	0	0	0	50	0	0	0	0	delegations comprising 23 Members (EU included), and representatives from	
23.06.2021	23.06.2021	ICCRAM	Online	Video / Film	ICCRAM - Medioambiente y sostenibilidad	Interview with project coordinator within institutional video	50	10	10	100	10	5	5	5	5	30 people in the room. 200 views. Published on ICCRAM TW,FB,LI	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=3Se8-3R9U https://www.diagonalproject.eu/video-featuring-
06.07.2021	09.07.2021	FORTH (George Voyatzis)	Thessaloniki (GR)-Hybrid multi-event	Participation to a conference	18th International Conference on Nanosciences & Nanotechnology	1 Oral Presentation: Physicochemical properties, transformation and degradation of nanomaterials	1000	500	0	0	200	0	100	0	200	over 2,000 researchers, scientists, engineers, business, technical and policy professionals	
13.07.2021		BNN	Online	Non-scientific and non-peer reviewed publications (popularised publications)	NanoSafety Cluster Newsletter "H2020 DIAGONAL spotlight"	Article featuring DIAGONAL in newsletter	200	50	0	50	14	0	0	0	0		https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5094676
26.07.2021	26.07.2021	BNN (Susanne Resch)	Online	Press release	DIAGONAL, a project bringing new methodologies to guarantee long-term nanosafety	Press release on website	500	200	10	50	20	10	0	0	0		https://www.diagonalproject.eu/diagonal-a-project-bringing-new-methodologies-to-guarantee-long-term-nanosafety/
01.09.2021	12.05.2022	ICCRAM	Online	Social media	36 Social Media publications (LI, FB, TW)	Post related to the Diagonal project	6 000	0	0	4200	0	0	0	0	0	3439 reach people only in FB	
24.09.2021	24.09.2021	ICCRAM	Burgos (ES)	Exhibition	"Understanding our environment"	ICCRAM team made different activities with children due to the European Researchers' Night	100	0	0	225	0	0	0	0	0		https://www.facebook.com/iccrsam.ubu/posts/2869561133359960
01.10.2021	31.10.2022	BNN (Caitlin Ahern)	Online	Website	DIAGONAL website	Total audience for website	537	215	54	82	40	40	54	0	107		
21.10.2021	22.10.2021	ISQ	Aveiro (PT)	Participation to a conference	Innovative approaches for risk management in nanotechnology	1 Poster presentation at 2nd SAM (Sustainable and Smart Advanced Manufacturing Meeting)											https://www.diagonalproject.eu/poster-presentation-university-of-aveiro/
07.12.2021		BRI (Sabine Jung-Wackli)	Online	Participation to a workshop	NanoSolveIT Workshop: IATA demonstration for	30 Tools in the NanoSolveIT Cloud Platform - feedback on scope of the											

17.12.2021		BRI (Stefanie Prenner)	Online	Participation to an event other than a	NanoSafety Cluster: Innovation and Safer by	Discussion on interpretation of SbD and SSbD. View from various NMMP-												
06.01.2022		QSAR Lab	Online	Social media	New Flyer - more about Diagonal Project	Information about the new Project Flyer - LinkedIn	200	100	100	585	100	0	85	0	0			https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6892015176934391808/
17.01.2022	17.01.2022	BNN (Susanne Resch)	Online	Flyer	DIAGONAL flyer	PDF version of flyer (# clicks)	30	15	0	5	4	0	0	0	0			
17.01.2022	04.05.2022	BNN (Susanne Resch)			DIAGONAL flyer	Printed version of flyer (# printed)	100	30	0	0	10	10	0	0	0			
20.01.2022	21.01.2022	ICCRAM	Burgos (ES)	Participation to a conference	ICCRAM scientific conference series	1 oral presentation: Our colleague Elizabeth Scamilla (Diagonal) explained her work	30	0	0	150	0	0	0	0	0	Published on ICCRAM TW,FB,LI		https://www.facebook.com/iccram.ubu/posts/2957110994604973
31.01.2022	31.01.2022	BNN (Susanne Resch)	Online	Participation to a workshop	NNI Public NanoEHS Webinar "What We Know about NanoEHS: Nanoinformatics and Modelling"		50	10	0	0	0	0	0	0	0			
10.02.2022	10.02.2022	ICCRAM	Burgos (ES)	Participation to a workshop	"Pollution Hunters"	Women and Science Week	500	0	0	580	0	0	0	0	0	Published on ICCRAM TW,FB,LI		https://www.facebook.com/iccram.ubu/posts/2970626473253425
22.03.2022	22.03.2022	BNN (Susanne Resch), BRI (Sabine Jung- Wackl)	Online	Participation to a workshop	EC - 2nd Safe and Sustainable by Design Stakeholder Workshop		150	150	0	0	100	0	0	0	0			
23.03.2022	23.03.2022	BNN (Susanne Resch)	Online	Participation to an event other than a conference or	IVL webinar on "A life cycle based chemicals assessment toolbox"		50	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0			
24.03.2022		BRI (Sabine Jung- Wackl)	Online	Participation to an event other than a conference or	Safe and Sustainable-by-Design: a key tool to boost innovation and growth;													
08.04.2022	08.04.2022	GXT	Online	Social media	DIAGONAL post	partnership GXT-DIAGONAL project	0	0	0	1049	0	0	0	0	0	175 YouTube Views		https://www.instagram.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6918098111680651264
08.04.2022	08.04.2022	GXT	Online	Social media	DIAGONAL post	partnership GXT-DIAGONAL project	0	0	0	211	0	0	0	0	0	321 YouTube Views		https://www.instagram.com/p/CcFEhh0ootn/?utm_source=ig_web_activity_share_sheet
08.04.2022	08.04.2022	GXT	Online	Social media	DIAGONAL post	partnership GXT-DIAGONAL project	0	0	0	225	0	0	0	0	0	25 registered people. Published on ICCRAM TW,FB,LI		https://www.facebook.com/grahenext/photos/pcb.6930412841866788864
02.05.2022	02.05.2022	BNN (Susanne Resch), BRI (Sabine Jung- Wackl)	Online	Participation to a workshop	EC RTD JRC Follow-up 2nd SSbD stakeholder workshop		100	100	0	0	50	0	0	0	0			
03.05.2022	03.05.2022	ICCRAM	Burgos (ES)	Press Release	ICCRAM cerró 2021 como su mejor año y comienza 2022 con dos nuevos proyectos europeos	Centre's progress with mention to DIAGONAL project (logo is down)	0	0	0	5000	0	0	0	0	0			https://www.ubu.es/noticia/iccram-cerro-2021-como-su-mejor-ano-y-comienza-2022-con-dos-proyectos-europeos
09.05.2022		BNN	Online	Non-scientific and non-peer reviewed publications (popularised publications)	NanoSafety Cluster Newsletter "NanoSafety Training School"	Article featuring NanoSafety Training school with DIAGONAL involvement	100	50	0	41	20	0	0	0	30			https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6532985
10.05.2022		QSAR Lab	Online	Website	Web News	Kick-off meeting	0	0	0	4000	0	0	0	0	0			https://www.qsarlab.com/en/diagonal-new-h2020-project/
11.05.2022	15.05.2022	ICCRAM	Online	Participation in activities organised jointly with other H2020 project(s)	DIAGONAL presentation at HARMLESS General Assembly	Talk	30	10	0	0	0	0	0	0	0			https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6930412841866788864
12.05.2022	03.05.2022	LIST (Arno Gutleb)	Luzern (CH)	Participation to a conference	Nanobehördendialog	Participation	25	0	0	0	25	0	0	0	0			
15.05.2022	20.05.2022	BNN (Susanne Resch)	Venice (IT)	Participation in activities organised jointly with other H2020 project(s)	Joint NanoSafety Training School 2022	Organization of joint event, presentations and flyers distributed. Training sessions and accompanying slides available.	90	10	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	Training with training materials (https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1E RI3EJhE0lq0MYe0pWcp515321u2LxT)		
08.06.2022	08.06.2022	ICCRAM	Burgos (ES)	Organisation of a workshop	Workshop with children	Our colleagues from ICCRAM carried out a great workshop in the Science and Technology Station (Burgos Spain), where children could	0	0	0	45	0	0	0	0	0			

16.06.2022	16.06.2022	Neovili	Online	Social media	Diagonal post	Post related to DIAGONAL leveraging on the Vivattech (tech event in Paris, France).	0	0	0	239	0	0	0	0	0	43 impressions, 11 engagements, 9 detail expands, 1 retweet	https://twitter.com/neovili/status/1537436740247375873?lang=en
20.06.2022	24.06.2022	Vireo (James Ede), BRI, (Q)SAR	Limassol (CY)	Participation to a conference	NanoWeek 2022	2 Poster & pitch presentations (Vireo, FORTH) 1 poster presentation (Q)SAR): Towards (Q)SAR/(Q)SPR modeling of multicomponent advanced nanomaterials	180	50	0	0	20	0	0	0	0		https://www.nanocongress.eu/nano-week-and-nanocongress-final-conference/
20.06.2022		BNN (Susanne Resch)	Limassol (CY)	Participation in activities organised jointly with other	NMBP-16 Ambassadors meeting		22	8	0	0	0	0	0	0	0		
24.06.2022		BNN (Caitlin Ahern)	Online	Non-scientific and non-peer reviewed publications (popularised publications)	BNN QUARTERLY	Article featuring DIAGONAL in newsletter (NanoSafety Training School)	214	86	0	21	22	22	21	0	43		
24.06.2022	24.06.2022	(Q)SAR Lab	Gdańsk (PL)	Participation to a conference	Application of in silico methods to assess the toxicity of new chemicals	1 Poster presentation at 2nd SAM (Sustainable and Smart, Advanced Manufacturing Meeting)	100	10	15	152	3	2	0	0	22		
30.06.2022		BNN (Caitlin Ahern)	Online	Video / Film	Video impressions of NanoWeek 2022	Compilation of photos and video from NanoWeek and Consortium Meeting	1200	400	0	500	50	50	0	0	38		
05.07.2022	05.07.2022	GXT	online	Social media	DIAGONAL post	DIAGONAL at Nanoweek (reposted)	0	0	0	397	0	0	0	0	0		https://www.linkedin.com/company/11106561/admin/
19.07.2022	22.07.2022	ICCRAM (Sara Rozas)	Coimbra (PT)	Participation to a conference	FEMS Euromat Junior Congress	1 Poster "First principles study of Co-Catalysed MgH2 for CO2 capture											
21.07.2022		ICCRAM-UBU	Burgos (ES)	Participation to a workshop	Workshop with children	Sandra Curiel, Juan José González and Blanca Velasco gave a workshop for children on the topic of nanomaterials.	0	0	0	30	0	0	0	0	0		
27.07.2022		ICCRAM-UBU	Online	Press release	Press release+social media	Nandita Dasgupta, from India to the UBU thanks to a María Zambrano scholarship–She will be involved in the development of nanomaterials.										https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6958033501845618688	https://www.ubu.es/nobias/nandita-dasgupta-de-india-la-ubu-gracias-una-beca-maria-zambrano
10.08.2022		(Q)SAR Lab	Online	Social media	About DIAGONAL	Information about the DIAGONAL LinkedIn	150	150	100	479	70	9	0	0	0		https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6963059611486547968/
23.08.2022		(Q)SAR Lab	Online	Social media	Correlative Materials Characterization	Information about a speech - LinkedIn	300	300	100	930	200	0	30	0	0		https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6967751047784095744/
02.09.2022		BNN	online	Non-scientific and non-peer reviewed publications (popularised publications)	NanoSafety Cluster Newsletter "DIAGONAL @ Nanoweek"	Article featuring DIAGONAL in newsletter	170	30	0	30	15	0	0	0	0		https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7043435 https://www.diagonalproject.eu/diagonal-nanosafety-cluster-newsletter-27/
16.09.2022		ICCRAM-UBU	Online	Participation to a conference	Iberoamerican Online Conference of Circular Economy	1 oral presentation: Jesús Ibáñez gave a talk at an event in Spanish focused on the key issues for economic recovery and circular transition in Iberoamerica.										https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6976157669355073536	https://youtu.be/CUjDR6s9QqI
22.09.2022		BNN (Susanne Resch)	Mestre (IT)	Participation to a workshop	NMBP-15/16 Stakeholder Workshop @BioCeramics32	Focus on SSbD paradigms from ongoing European projects incl. DIAGONAL	40	20	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	Workshop	
30.09.2022		BNN (Caitlin Ahern)	St. Pölten (AT)	Exhibition	European Researchers' Night	Booth with BNN and other projects on nanomaterials	45	0	200	200	0	5	0	0	50		
12.10.2022		(Q)SAR Lab	Dresden, Germany	Participation to a workshop	Microscopy and Materials Characterization - In silico methods for characterization	1 oral Presentation	200	50	0	10	10	0	0	0	0		
13.10.2022	14.10.2022	(Q)SAR Lab	Dresden, Germany	Participation to a workshop	Correlative Materials Characterization – poster – In silico materials	1 Poster & pitch presentation	200	100	100	500	15	25	25	0	35		
17.10.2022		BNN (Caitlin Ahern)	Online	Non-scientific and non-peer reviewed publications	BNN QUARTERLY	Article featuring DIAGONAL in newsletter (BioCeramics32)	220	88	0	22	22	22	22	0	44		
17.10.2022		(Q)SAR Lab	Online	Social media	Correlative Materials Characterization	About the poster and presentation - LinkedIn	600	500	400	2017	400	50	50	17	0		https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6987670598298570752/

20.10.2022	BNN (Susanne Resch)	Online	Participation to a workshop	RESISTANT Final Workshop		16	9	0	0	0	0	0	0	0						
END OF REPORTING PERIOD 1 - 31 Oct 2022						TOTALS						21038	6239	1209	27139	2115	966	546	113	1993
08.11.2022	ICCRAM-UBU + WUR+ Phornano	Ljubljana	Participation in activities organised jointly with other H2020 project(s)	Week of Microbial Technologies	1 oral presentation - Roundtable - materials science section - speakers have given an overview of colloid biology on material sciences. 1 Poster presentation: Study of	100	100	0	100	50	20	0	0	0	Topics included the study and prediction of material's toxicology to develop safe by design nanomaterials, applications of biofilms and guidances to manufacture nanomaterials in a sustainable way.	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6995797543540396032				
11.11.2022	NEOVILI (Milena Amaral)	Paris, France	Participation to a conference	Paris Peace Forum	Multistakeholder avenue, networking	250	3000	80	0	600	100	0	0	0						
15.11.2022	BNN (Susanne Resch)	Online	Participation to a workshop	Joint EU H2020 HARMLESS/OECD SG AdMa workshop		20	20	0	0	5	0	0	0	5	Meeting with standardization body					
17.11.2022	ICCRAM UBU	Online	Video / Film	MicroTechWeek video	Summary video of the event. Diagonal as clustering project	200	200	0	200	50	50	0	0	0	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6999034931284762626					
17.11.2022	ICCRAM UBU	Online	Non-scientific and non-peer reviewed publications (popularised publications)	MicroTechWeek blog post - popularised article	The Week of Microbial Technologies was a great success	200	50	0	200	0	10	0	0	0	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7000373197619511297					
21.11.2022	ICCRAM UBU	Online	Press release	Press release+social media	ICCRAM's success as co-organiser of MicroTechWeek	500	100	0	100	0	100	0	0	0						
21.11.2022	ICCRAM-UBU	Sitges (Barcelona, Spain)	Participation to a conference	21st International Congress of the European Society of Toxicology In Vitro (ESTIV 2022)	2 posters related to DIAGONAL project by Carlos Rumbo and Natalia Fernández	1000	0	0	500	0	0	0	0	0	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7000747664485027840					
21.11.2022	NEOVILI (Milena Amaral)	Online	Participation to a conference	Découplages ressources, production et performance éco-socio-environnementale	Networking	20	12	0	0	0	0	0	0	0						
23.11.2022	NEOVILI (Milena Amaral)	Online	Participation to a conference	Meet-up urgence environnementale & crise énergétique	Networking	5	80	0	0	3	0	0	0	0						
25.11.2022	NEOVILI (Milena Amaral)	Online	Participation to a workshop	Workshop on the application of SSbD concept in materials and chemicals (IRISS)	Networking	40	6	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	https://events.blackthorn.io/en/0135ERM7/workshop-on-the-application-of-ssbd-concept-in-materials-					
25.11.2022		Online	Participation in activities organised jointly with other H2020 project(s)	Webinar: IRISS workshop on the application of the SSbD concept in materials and chemicals											Webinar	https://www.diagonalproiect.eu/diagonal-iriss-workshop/				
06.12.2022	Vireo (James Ede)	Tampa, FL (US)	Participation to a conference	Society for Risk Analysis (SRA) Meeting 2022	1 Oral Presentation of Diagonal Project work: Life-cycle Risk Assessment of Consumer Applications of Graphene: Outcomes, Data Gaps and Priorities															
12.12.2022	NEOVILI (Milena Amaral)	Online	Participation to a conference	Consumption and environment in Europe's circular economy	Networking	55	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	https://www.instagram.com/p/CmAE8K1m4?utm_source=ig_web_copy_link&igshid=MzRlODBiNWFlZA					
13.12.2022	BRI (Sabine Jung-Wackl)	Online	Participation in activities organised jointly with other H2020 project(s)	NSC Working Group D Working Meeting	Planning for 2023															
13.12.2022	NEOVILI (Milena Amaral)	Online	Participation to a workshop	Driving long-term recovery and economic growth by building a trusted, sustainable, and inclusive digital future	Networking	60	40	27	0	300	0	0	0	0	https://www.oecd-events.org/digital-ministerial/en					
21.12.2022	ICCRAM (Natalia Fernández)		Non-scientific and non-peer reviewed publications (popularised publications)	BNN QUARTERLY 04/2022	Article featuring DIAGONAL in newsletter ((Nano)materials Characterization: Novel Techniques & Tools and Their Contribution to Standardization)	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	See BNN QUARTERLY entry below for audience statistics	BNN Quarterly 04_2022.pdf				

11.01.2023		BRI (Sabine Jung-Wackl)	Online	Participation to a workshop	Workshop: from the Materials2030 Manifesto towards a Strategic Agenda for advanced materials													
16.01.2023		BNN, BRI	Online	Participation in activities organised jointly with other H2020 project(s)	NMBP-16 Ambassadors Meeting	Meeting of the 3 NMBP-16 projects for update on the status in the different Task forces	14	10	0	0	0	0	0	0	0			
19.01.2023		GXT	Online	Social media	Exposure Campaign	Exposure Campaign in GXT	0	0	0	250	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	Linkedin 174 Organic Impressions, 4 reactions.
19.01.2023		GXT	Online	Social media	Exposure Campaign	Exposure Campaign in GXT	0	0	0	1934	0	0	0	0	0			https://www.linkedin.com/posts/graphenext_graphenext/m_facebook.com/graphenext/photos/a.60019
19.01.2023		GXT	Online	Social media	Exposure Campaign	Exposure Campaign in GXT	0	0	0	316	0	0	0	0	0			https://www.instagram.com/n/CmAFBKI.mA7a.m
19.01.2023	19.01.2023	NEOVILI (Mílina Amaral)	Online	Participation to a workshop	OECD / IOMC Workshops: Strengthening global action to advance chemicals and waste management	Networking												
24.01.2023	24.01.2023	NEOVILI (Mílina Amaral)	Online	Participation to a workshop	OECD / Workshop: exploring innovation trends	Networking	0	20	0	0	60	0	0	0	0			
31.01.2023		BRI (Sabine Jung-Wackl)	Online	Participation in activities organised jointly with other H2020 project(s)	Future-proof Approaches for Risk Governance – Lessons Learned from Nanomaterials	To ensure that results from the projects (NanoRigo, RiskGone, Gov4Nano) are taken up to support the implementation of the Chemical Strategy for Sustainability (CSS) and												
02.02.2023		Vireo (Fiona Case)	Online	Website	Nano and advanced materials: safe and sustainable by design	Blog post highlighting Diagonal project work in "Status, implications and challenges of European safe and sustainable by design paradigms applicable to nanomaterials and advanced materials" published in RSC Sustainability journal today.												
05.02.2023		Vireo (James Ede)	Online	Social media	Seeking input on the public image of "safe and sustainable by design"	Invitation to participate in the survey provided by SAbYNA.	0	0	0	300	0	0	0	0	0			
09.02.2023	10.02.2023	BNN (Susanne Resch), BRI (Stefanie Prenner)	Brussels / Online	Participation to a workshop	EC Stakeholder workshop on Safe and Sustainable by Design case studies		175	85	0	0	40	0	0	0	0			
13.02.2023	16.02.2023	NEOVILI (Mílina Amaral)	Paris, France (OECD)	Participation to a workshop	OECD / Forum on Due Diligence for Garments and Footwear	Networking												https://www.oecd.org/industry/mn/reponsible-supply-chains-textile-garment-sector.htm
16.02.2023		BRI (Stefanie Prenner)	Online	Participation to a workshop	WORKSHOP International Nanosafety and Nanostandardization: Status, Gaps, Needs and the Role of INISS	Presentation and discussion of the current status, gaps, needs and the role of INISS within nanosafety and nanostandardization												https://www.bnn.at/events/iniss-workshop/#register
27.02.2023		BNN (Susanne Resch, Beatriz Alfaro)	Online	Participation in activities organised jointly with other H2020 project(s)	[NMBP-15/16] Joint Stakeholder Engagement Core Group TelCo #16	Regular NMBP-15/-16 projects meeting for updating on own/joint Stakeholder Engagement activities and possible collaborations	2	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0			https://www.nanosafe.org/cea-tech/pns/nanosafe/en
07.03.2023		BNN	Online	Non-scientific and non-peer reviewed publications (popularised publications)	Article @ BNN QUARTERLY 01/2023	Article about the NMBP-16 Ambassadors Meeting which took place on 16 January 2023 (page 39).	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*	*		See below for audience statistics	https://www.bnn.at/wp-content/uploads/2023/03/BNN_Quarterly_01_2023.pdf
09.03.2023	09.03.2023	Neovil	Brussels	Participation to a conference	"Tisser l'industrie européenne de demain: un processus de coopération" / "Forging the Future of the European Industry: A Collaborative Journey"	Roundtable discussion	0	50	0	0	10	0	0	0	0			In the context of regulating the textile industry, this round table provides a valuable platform for fostering dialogue between fashion industry professionals and representatives from European Institutions. The event aims to delve into the EU legislative process, shedding light

09.03.2023	09.03.2023	NEOVILI (Milena Amaral)	Brussels	Participation to a conference	Tisser /Industrie européenne de demain: un processus de coopération	Networking	12	0	13	0	4	0	0	0	0	
23.04.2023	29.04.2023	QSAR Lab (Alicja Mikolajczyk)	Galapagos	Participation to a conference	NSSY 2023	1 Oral Presentation: Safe and Sustainability-by-design: Challenges and advanced in computational design of advance materials	120	0	0	0	10	0	0	0	100	
09.05.2023	10.05.2023	WUR (Henk van Lingen)	Egmond aan Zee	Participation to a conference	Bioinformatics & Systems Biology Conference 2023 (BioSB)	1 poster: Exploring RNA-seq data normalization methods using principal component analysis and KEGG pathway enrichment										https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10528478
15.05.2023	19.05.2023	BNN (Susanne Resch)	Venice	Organisation of a workshop	NanoSafety Training School 2023	Susanne Resch (BNN) chaired 4 sessions (on FAIR data management, How to make my method ready for regulatory acceptance, and Implementation of platforms)	120	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
16.05.2023	17.05.2023	UBU, LIST, DTI, Monolithos	Burgos	Organisation of a conference	Safe and sustainable by design strategies towards innovation	Organization of conference and 3 oral presentations from DIAGONAL	30	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	https://www.eventim.com/programa/10528478/a/conferencia-sobre-sostenibilidad-e-innovacion-safe-and-
17.05.2023		Vireo (James Ede)	Online	Social media	Project partners meeting in Spain	Creating awareness of DIAGONAL and driving traffic to the website	0	0	0	300	0	0	0	0	0	Linkedin: 148 Organic Impressions. Twitter: 48 views, 33 reactions, one re-tweet
25.05.2023		Vireo (James Ede)	Online	Non-scientific and non-peer reviewed publications (popularised publications)	BioNanoEHS News	The May 2023 edition of the Vireo Newsletter included news/information about the Diagonal Project.	0	0	0	393	0	0	0	0	0	38% open rate
25.05.2023		BRI (Sabine Jung)	Online	Participation to a workshop	HARMLESS workshop on Safe-and-Sustainable-by-Design (SSbD) for SMEs: Advanced Materials in Product Development	Introduction to HARMLESS approach to integration of SSbD principles in AdMe-enhanced product development.	25	25	0	0	3	0	0	0	6	
05.06.2023	09.06.2023	BNN (Susanne Resch, Beatriz Alfaro)	Grenoble	Participation in activities organised jointly with other H2020 project(s)	nanoSAFE & NSC Week 2023: NMBP-16 Ambassadors Meeting		15	12	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	https://www.nanosafe.org/cea-tech/pns/nanosafe/en
05.06.2023	09.06.2023	ICCRAM (Natalia Fernández), ITENE, BNN	Grenoble	Participation to a conference	nanoSAFE & NSC Week 2023	1 oral presentation (LIST): Use of realistic advanced in vitro methods for safety assessment of MCNMs/HARNs 2 Poster presentation	109	50	0	0	10	0	0	0	40	Linkedin: 91 organic impressions, 3 reactions, one repost, Twitter: 39 views, 2 reactions, one re-tweet
05.06.2023		BRI (Sabine Jung-Wacik)	Online	Participation to a conference	SABYDOMA's 2nd Legal Workshop on Safe-and-Sustainable-by-Design (SSbD)											
06.06.2023	07.06.2023	NEOVILI (Milena Amaral)	Online	Participation to a conference	EU Green Week	Networking	60	0	0	0	0	150	0	0	0	
11.06.2023	13.06.2023	QSAR Lab (Alicja Mikolajczyk)	Lund	Participation to a conference	Euro Nano Forum 2023	Poster: Safe and Sustainability-by-design: Towards QSAR modelling of multicomponent, advanced nanomaterials	100	50	0	0	10	0	0	0	20	
11.06.2023	13.06.2023	BNN (Andreas Falk)	Lund	Exhibition	Euro Nano Forum 2023	Joint booth NMBP-15/-16 projects - Roll-up & poster prepared	200	80	0	0	50	10	0	0	0	
15.06.2023	15.06.2023	QSAR Lab (Alicja Mikolajczyk)	Online	Social media	A linkedin post about dr Alicja Mikolajczyk activity during the Euro Nano Forum 23'	Safe and Sustainability-by-design: Towards QSAR modelling of multicomponent, advanced nanomaterials -promotion of activity during Euro Nano Forum 23'	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1441	
21.06.2023		BNN (Andreas Falk), 4N	Berlin	Participation to a workshop	6th EU-Asia Dialogue on NanoSafety		45	15	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	

25.06.2023	28.06.2023	ICCRAM (Dalia de la Fuente)	Burgos	Participation to a conference	XXIX Congress of the SEM	1 Poster presentation: Desarrollo de una metodología para evaluar el impacto toxicológico de nuevos nanomateriales sobre biofilms bacterianos	400	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	https://www.semiconologia.org/en/news/xxix-congress-of-the-sem
29.06.2023		BNN	Online	Non-scientific and non-peer reviewed publications (popularised)	Article (1) @ BNN Quarterly 02/2023 (page 11-13)	Article about impressions from the 12th NanoSafety Training School on Safe and Sustainable by Design Approaches for Chemicals.	1515	390	0	0	390	140	0	0	465			
29.06.2023		BNN	Online	Non-scientific and non-peer reviewed publications (popularised)	Article (2) @ BNN Quarterly 02/2023 (page 21-23)	Article about the participation at the nanoSAFE 2023 and NSC Joint Conference	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	https://www.diagonalprote ct.eu/diagonal-bnn-quarterly-june-2023/
29.06.2023		BNN	Online	Non-scientific and non-peer reviewed publications (popularised)	Article (3) @ BNN Quarterly 02/2023 (page 24-26)	Article about the participation at the ENF	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	https://www.diagonalprote ct.eu/diagonal-bnn-quarterly-june-2023/
29.06.2023		BNN	Online	Non-scientific and non-peer reviewed publications (popularised publications)	Article (4) @ BNN Quarterly 02/2023 (page 64)	Article about the NMBP-16 Meeting in Grenoble	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
30.06.2023		Vireo (James Ede)	Online	Social media	A new modelling study reveals the structure of fluids in the presence of nanostructured materials	Highlighting project partner paper: Understanding the impact of nanostructured materials on liquids/solvents is key to the development of safe by design tools	0	0	0	300	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
04.07.2023		BNN	Online	Video / Film	DIAGONAL tours ICCRAM labs	Walk-through tour of ICCRAM facilities during consortium meeting	100	50	10	10	10	5	0	0	0	6		https://nanotechia.org/events/na-symposium-2023
07.07.2023		BNN (Beatriz Afaro, Susanne Resch)	Online	Participation in activities organised jointly with other H2020 project(s)	(NMBP-15/16) Joint Stakeholder Engagement Core Group TelCo #19	Regular NMBP-15/-16 projects meeting for updating on own/joint Stakeholder Engagement activities and possible collaborations	2	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
25.08.2023		GXT	Online	Social media	Diagonal post - Facebook	Promotion of Diagonal Project	0	0	0	68	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	https://www.instagram.com/nanobioadvisors/
25.08.2023		GXT	Online	Social media	Diagonal post - LinkedIn	Promotion of Diagonal Project	0	0	0	516	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6916211121807272800
25.08.2023		GXT	Online	Social media	Diagonal post - Instagram	Promotion of Diagonal Project	0	0	0	89	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	https://www.instagram.com/nanobioadvisors/
05.09.2023		ICCRAM	Online	Participation in activities organised jointly with other H2020 project(s)	NMBP-16 Coordinators meeting	Meeting between the 3 NMBP-16 coordinators to address joint upcoming NMBP-16 collaborations/activities	3	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
06.09.2023	08.09.2023	ICCRAM, NEWILI (Milena Amaral)	Lille, France	Participation to a conference	11th International Conference on Life Cycle Management	2 Poster presentations , 1 oral presentation (social panel), networking	1400	0	0	0	6	0	0	0	0	0	0	https://www.lcm2023.org
14.09.2023		BRI (Stefanie Prenner), BNN (Susanne Resch)	Vienna	Participation to a conference	15th NanoTrust Conference	Networking	70	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	
19.09.2023		Vireo	Online	Non-scientific and non-peer reviewed publications (popularised publications)	Nano and sustainable materials: testing, commercialization and regulatory roundup	Promotion of a paper highlighting progress on DIAGONAL Project work.												https://www.vireoadvisors.com/blog/nano-and-sustainable-materials-testing-commercialization-and-regulatory-roundup-2
22.09.2023		BRI (Stefanie Prenner)	Online	Participation to a workshop	Training for SMEs: Safe-and-Sustainable-by-Design tools and case studies													
27.09.2023		BNN	Online	Non-scientific and non-peer reviewed publications (popularised)	Article in BNN (QUARTERLY 03/2023)	Announcement ANTHOS / DIAGONAL workshop in BNN QUARTERLY	1515	390	0	0	390	140	0	0	465			https://www.bnn.at/bnn-quarterly-03-2023/
29.09.2023		BNN	Graz, AT	Exhibition	European Researchers' Night 2023	Booth with hands-on activities about nanomaterials and DIAGONAL flyers	100	0	10	230	0	10	0	0	0	0	0	
12.10.2023		BRI (Stefanie Prenner)	Online	Participation in activities organised jointly with other H2020 project(s)	NMBP-16 SEE Ambassadors meeting		5	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	Stakeholder engagement

13.10.2023		NovaM	Online	Non-scientific and non-peer reviewed publications (popularised publications)	ECHA Nanopinion	Article titled "Unlocking the potential of in silico modelling and read-across approaches for nanomaterials: insights from case studies"	#	#	#	#	#	#	#	#	#	#	#	https://eun.echa.europa.eu/nanopinion/ https://unlocking-the-potential-of-in-silico-modelling-and-read-across-approaches	
16.10.2023	16.10.2023	Q&SAR Lab (Alicja Mikolajczyk)	Krakow/ Poland	Participation to a conference	Nanotomography Minisymposium	1 Oral presentation: Advanced 3D data analysis with AI-based algorithms	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	400				
07.11.2023		BRI (Stefanie Prenner)	Vienna, AT	Participation to a workshop	Workshop „EU-Chemikalienstrategie für Nachhaltigkeit – Österreichische Roadmap zu Safe-and-Sustainable-by-Design“	Final presentation and workshop of two Austrian projects dealing with the topic of SSbD.	14	1	0	0	2	0	0	0	0				
10.11.2023	11.11.2023	NEOWILI (Milena Amaral)	Paris, France	Participation to a conference	Paris Peace Forum	Multistakeholder avenue, networking	250	3000	80	0	600	100	0	0	0	Stakeholder engagement		https://parispeaceforum.org/fr/notre-impact/	
05.12.2023		Vireo (Jo Anne Shatkin)	Online	Participation to a conference	Nanotechnology Industries Association (NIA) Symposium	Invited panelist for a discussion on Creating the right regulatory environment for nanomaterial innovation. Plus Networking.	500	300	300	20	100	7	45	0	0				
05.12.2023		BRI (Stefanie Prenner)	Online	Organisation of a workshop	TRAAC Workshop on the DIAGONAL Nanotube Construction Tool	Evaluation of the Nanotube Construction Tool based on the 5 pillars of the TRAAC framework	17	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	Workshop			
06.12.2023	07.12.2023	BRI (Stefanie Prenner)	Online	Participation to a workshop	Safe and Sustainable by Design: 4th Stakeholders Workshop	Feedback from the 1st reporting period													
06.12.2023	07.12.2023	NEOWILI (Milena Amaral)	Brussels	Participation to a workshop	CBE JU Stakeholder Forum	Multistakeholder avenue, networking													
07.12.2023		NovaM	Online	Training	Internal SciNote Training		12	6	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	Training			
10.12.2023		Vireo (James Ede, Jo Anne Shatkin, Yueyang Zhang)	Washington DC, USA	Participation to a conference	The Society for Risk Analysis Annual Meeting	1 oral presentation: latest work on nanomaterials for regulatory and toxicological assessments, and discussed the results of our Diagonal Project work with attendees.	500	200	75	0	150	5	45	50	0			https://www.wcdsystem.com/stra/program/SSGx5m7/index.cfm?abid=78696&sqid=8008&sid=32500	
12.12.2023	12.12.2023	RINA-UK	Coventry, UK	Participation to a conference	FM3 (Future Materials, Minerals & Mining Conference)	1 Oral presentation: Promotion of our Diagonal Project work	70	10	0	0	0	0	0	0	0			https://www.iam3.org/events-awards/ems-event-calendar/future-materials-minerals-mining-	
16.10.2023	16.10.2023	Q&SAR Lab (Alicja Mikolajczyk)	Cracow, Poland	Participation to a conference	Nanotomography Minisymposium	1 Oral presentation: Advanced 3D data analysis with AI-based algorithms	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	300				
14.12.2023		Vireo	Online	Social media	Life-cycle risk assessment of graphene-enabled textiles in fire protection gear	Sharing results of work carried out as part of the Diagonal Project to LinkedIn	0	0	0	206	0	0	0	0	0	206 Impressions 21 Engagements 7 Reposts		https://www.vireoadvisors.com/blog/life-cycle-risk-assessment-of-graphene-enabled-textiles-in-fire-protection-gear	
14.12.2023		Vireo	Online	Non-scientific and non-peer reviewed publications (popularised publications)	Life-cycle risk assessment of graphene-enabled textiles in fire protection gear	Promotion of our Diagonal Project work													
16.10.2023		ICRAM	Burgos	Exhibition	European Researchers' Night 2023		0	0	30	0	0	0	0	0	0			https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7119634328883503105	
18.12.2023		ICRAM	Brussels	Participation to a conference	4th Stakeholder Workshop on Safe and Sustainable by Design	1 Oral presentation: Natalia Fernández (ICRAM Toxicology research line) made a presentation related to the application of the SSbD framework to novel materials for Key Enabling Technologies, with multiple applications for research purposes, based on DIAGONAL work.	300	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0				
END OF REPORTING PERIOD 2							9950	8361	595	6032	2853	847	90	50	3288				
TOTAL CUMULATIVE RP1 & RP2							30988	14600	1804	33171	4968	1813	636	163	5281				

10.01.2024		BRI (Stefanie Prenner)	Online	Organisation of a workshop	TRAAC workshop on the DIAGONAL Uptake & bioaccumulation of NMs model	Evaluation of the uptake & bioaccumulation of NMs model based on the 5 pillars of the TRAAC framework	20	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	Workshop
11.01.2024		BNN (Susanne Resch)	Helsinki	Training	Bilateral training BNN/ECHA nano team	Bilateral training session between BNN and ECHA nano team to discuss crucial domains in nanomaterials' safety and sustainability	7	0	0	0	7	0	0	0	0	0	Training / Meeting with Regulatory Body
12.01.2024		Vireo	Online	Social media	A new paper from our DIAGONAL project partners	Sharing results of work carried out as part of the Diagonal Project to LinkedIn	0	0	0	147	0	0	0	0	0	0	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7151448662370324480
08.02.2024		Vireo	Online	Social media	Call for abstracts opens today for NanoTox 2024!	Sharing Diagonal Project post with our community and encouraging submissions for NanoTox 2024	0	0	0	98	0	0	0	0	0	0	https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7161408271415660546
13.02.2024		Vireo	Online	Social media	n/a	Announcing on LinkedIn that the paper on the Nano LCRA carried out with DIAGONAL partners is open access.	0	0	0	100	0	0	0	0	0	0	
29.02.2024		Vireo	Online	Social media	n/a	Repost of DIAGONAL post demonstrating graphene reinforced metallic coatings on X.											
04.03.2024	07.03.2024	ICCRAM, BNN	Vienna	Organisation of a conference	ANTHOS24	Organization (BNN) of conference for NMBP-15 and-16 projects. Oral presentation (ICCRAM) Roundtable discussion (ICCRAM), workshop (IZES), participation from OCSIAL, Cnano, ITENE	95	31	3	2	5	0	0	0	0	27	
07.03.2024		IZES	Vienna	Organisation of a workshop	Expert Workshop on Public Perceptions of Nanoparticles in Sunscreens: Challenges and Opportunities	Workshop within ANTHOS to discuss public trust towards nanotechnology and nanoparticles in sunscreens	14	2	1	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	workshop
18.03.2024		Vireo	Online	Social media	The call for abstracts opens today for the 11th International Conference on NanoToxicology – NanoTox 2024!	Promoting conference organized by Projects DIAGONAL, HARMLESS, and h2020 SUNSHINE.	0	0	0	156	0	0	0	0	0	0	
21.03.2024		BNN, ICCRAM	Online	Non-scientific and non-peer reviewed publications (popularised publications)	BNN (QUARTERLY 2024/01	Interview with DIAGONAL coordinator on SSbD, MCNMs, HARNs	1780	470	150	800	470	160	0	0	0	0	
25.03.2024		BRI (Stefanie Prenner)	Online	Participation in activities organised jointly with other H2020 project(s)	NMBP-16 Ambassadors Meeting	Meeting of the 3 NMBP-16 projects for update on the status in the different Task forces											
07.04.2024	11.04.2024	OCSIAL, FORTH (Gunther Van Kerckhove)	Strasbourg (France)	Participation to a conference	ChemOnTubes 2024 Conference	1 Oral presentation: Gunther Van Kerckhove (OCSIAL) made a presentation "Raman spectroscopy elucidates the transformation of single-walled carbon nanotubes following abrasive wear of epoxy coatings"	100	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	https://chemontubes2024.sciencesconf.org/2lanq=en
25.04.2024		BRI (Stefanie Prenner)	Online	Participation to an event other than a conference or workshop	HARMLESS webinar on Safe-and-Sustainable-by-Design (SSbD) for consultancy companies, SME and large industry: Demonstration of the user-friendly HARMLESS Decision Support System (DSS) with an advanced material as a case study												

08.07.2024	12.07.2024	ICCRAM	Lüneburg	Training	10th Summer School on Sustainable Chemistry at LEuphana	1 Poster: Social Life Cycle Assessment of new silver nanowires by Patricia De La Fuente															Training?	
18.07.2024		BNN, BRI	Online	Video / Film	Video: DIAGONAL SSbD Decision Support Tool	Video posted to YouTube, social media and project website explaining the DIAGONAL SSbD Decision Support Tool in an animation																
24.07.2024		Vireo	Online	Social media	n/a	Promoting a video from DIAGONAL on LinkedIn introducing their Decision Support Tool.	0	0	0	127	0	0	0	0	0							
03.09.2024		BRI (Stefanie Prenner)	Online	Participation to an event other than a conference or workshop	Roadmap "Towards Safe and Sustainable Advanced and Innovative Materials"																	
03.09.2024		BNN	Online	Participation in activities organised jointly with other H2020 project(s)	Webinar: EU NanoSafety Cluster Roadmap "Towards Safe and Sustainable Advanced and Innovative Materials"	1 oral presentation on Training and Outreach activities (including those carried out within DIAGONAL) within EU NSC Roadmap webinar															Webinar	
08.09.2024	13.09.2024	LIST (Antje Biesemeier)	La Rochelle, France	Participation to a conference	24th International Conference on Secondary Ion Mass Spectrometry (SIMS-24)	1 Oral presentation: Improving the analysis of biological samples incorporating nanoparticles by multimodal imaging and mass spectrometry applied on focused ion beam instrumentation	70	10	0	0	70	0	0	0	0							
09.09.2024		BRI (Stefanie Prenner)	Online	Participation in activities organised jointly with other H2020 project(s)	[NMBP-16] SEE Ambassadors Meeting	TaskForce Stakeholder Engagement and Exploitation																
13.09.2024		BRI (Stefanie Prenner)	Online	Participation to an event other than a conference or workshop	PHOENIX (EU funded project) Satellite Event at ECCPM - PHOENIX: A new player bridging nano-pharmaceutical innovation from design to clinic		20	12	0	0	0	0	0	0	0							
16.09.2024		BNN	Brussels, Belgium	Participation to an event other than a conference or workshop	Joint European Forum for IPCEIs - Workshop of the Clean Tech Working Group	Industry Workshop, IPCEI AdMa BNN represents the NSC community in the Advance Materials ecosystem (IPCEI)	15	25	0	0	10	0	0	0	0							
18.09.2024	31.10.2024	BNN	Online	Communication campaign (e.g. radio TV)	How "nano" is the world around you?	Quiz for the general public to increase awareness about nanomaterials in their daily lives																
23.09.2024	25.09.2024	ICCRAM, BNN	Venice	Organisation of a conference	NanoTox 2024 - 11th International Conference on NanoToxicology		120	80	0	0	10	0	0	0	0							
23.09.2024	25.09.2024	OCSIA (Gunther Van Kerckhove), BRI	Venice	Participation to a conference	NanoTox 2024 - 11th International Conference on NanoToxicology	1 Oral presentation: Gunther Van Kerckhove (OCSIA) made a presentation "Risk assessment along the life cycle of TUBALL™ nanocomposites." Participation by several partners.	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-						https://www.nanotox2024.eu/	
23.09.2024		BNN	Online	Non-scientific and non-peer reviewed publications (popularised publications)	BNN QUARTERLY 2024/03	Article about MaterialsWeek in the September 2024 digital magazine on sustainable technologies	2330	635	220	810	630	220	0	0	0							https://www.diagonaleurope.eu/diagonal-bnn-quarterly-sept-2024/
24.09.2024		BNN	Online	Non-scientific and non-peer reviewed publications (popularised publications)	EU NanoSafetyCluster Update	DIAGONAL webinar mentioned in update	1000	410	10	10	15	10	10	10	10						1475 total recipients	

25.09.2024		BRI (Stefanie Prenner), BNN	Venice	Participation in activities organised jointly with other H2020 project(s)	NMBP-16 Ambassadors Meeting	Final meeting of the 3 NMBP-16 projects for update on the status in the different Task forces	17	8	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
25.09.2024		UBU, BNN, ITENE	Venice	Participation in activities organised jointly with other H2020 project(s)	NMBP-16 Public Final Event	Co-organization of showcase of key achievements of the 3 sister projects, including KERs and the legacy of each project	35	15	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
25.09.2024	31.10.2024	BNN	Online	Communication campaign (e.g. radio TV)	Nano-awareness Survey for SMEs	Survey and resources for SMEs to identify where they might be producing nanoparticles and where to turn for guidance on SSbD									
27.09.2024		BNN	Graz	Exhibition	European Researchers' Night - Life is Science	Booth at public science event on nanomaterials and interactive quiz "how nano is the world around you?"	120	10	10	500	0	10	0	0	0
27.09.2024		BNN	Graz	Video / Film	European Researchers' Night - Life is Science	Short video on BNN activities at ERN 2024.	45	17	5	5	5	5	5	5	5
22.10.2024	25.10.2024	BRI (Stefanie Prenner)	Thessaloniki, Greece	Participation to a workshop	2nd Safe and Sustainable by Design boot camp										
15.10.2024		BNN	Online	Non-scientific and non-peer reviewed publications (popularised publications)	BNN INFORMS 2024-19	Highlight of DIAGONAL webinar in BioNanoNet members-only email newsletter	130	50	10	10	10	5	0	0	0
18.10.2024		GXT	Online	Social media	Reposted Diagonal post	Webinar: Introducing the DIAGONAL SSbD Decision Support Tool for Innovative Advanced Materials									
19.10.2024		BNN	Online	Video / Film	Impressions from NanoTox 2024	Video recapping the NanoTox conference with DIAGONAL contributions	400	200	10	10	10	5	8	5	0
23.10.2024		BNN	Online	Non-scientific and non-peer reviewed publications (popularised publications)	NSC Update #10 - October 2024	Nano-Awareness Survey for SMEs and DST webinar included in newsletter	1000	290	10	10	10	10	10	10	10
31.Okt		ITENE, NOvaM	Online	Organisation of a workshop	Webinar: Introducing the DIAGONAL SSbD Decision Support Tool	Webinar for the public on the KER of DIAGONAL - the Decision Support Tool - using a case study	30	10	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
During the whole project		BRI	Online	Other	Expert interviews	Interviews with experts from various fields to inform the exploitation activities									
Total Reporting Period 3							8303	2548	479	3726	1319	435	33	30	102
Total Project							39291	17148	2283	36897	6287	2248	669	193	5383

46 views on YouTube; 602 views on LinkedIn

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=HoxVf0xRt4>

Webinar

Annex 2: DIAGONAL Scientific Publications

Scientific Publications

List of Scientific Publications related to the project

#	Type (select from dropdown list)	Title	Author (s)	Partners Involved	Title of Journal/Proceedings	Number, date or frequency	Is peer-reviewed? (Y/N)	Is Open Access? (choose from dropdown)	DOI	Repository Link	Year	Journal Impact Score	# Article views	# Citations
1	Article in Journal	NanoMixHamster: a web-based tool for predicting cytotoxicity of TiO ₂ -based multicomponent nanomaterials towards Chinese Hamster Ovary (CHO-K1) cells	Filip Stoliński, Anna Rybińska-Fryca, Maciej Gromelski, Alicja Mikolajczyk*, Tomasz Puzyn*	QSAR	Nanotoxicology		1 Yes	Gold Open Access	10.1080/17435390.2022.2080609	https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/17435390.2022.2080609	2022	5.913	851	3
2	Article in Journal	High Catalytic Efficiency of a Nanosized Copper-Based Catalyst for Automotives: A Physicochemical Characterization	Soto Beobide, A.; Moschovi, A.M.; Mathioudakis, G.N.; Kourtelesis, M.; Lada, Z.G.; Andrikopoulos, K.S.; Sygellou, L;	FORTH, MONOLITHOS	Molecules	2022, 27, 7402.	Yes	Gold Open Access	10.3390/molecules27217402	https://www.mdpi.com/1420-3049/27/21/7402	2022	4.927	2010	2
3	Article in Journal	Low Toxicological Impact of Commercial Pristine Multi-Walled Carbon Nanotubes on the Yeast <i>Saccharomyces cerevisiae</i> .	Sonia Martel Martin; Rocio Barros; Brixhilda Domi; Carlos Rumbo; Matteo Poddighe; Santiago Aparicio; Maria Suarez-Diez; Juan	ICCRAM, WUR	Nanomaterials	11(9)	Yes	Gold Open Access	10.3390/nano11092272	https://www.mdpi.com/2079-4991/11/9/2272#	2022	4.921	2790	3
4	Publication in conference proceedings/workshop	Towards safety and sustainability in scalable production of semiconducting nano- and non-nanomaterials: Zinc oxide - a case study	Farias, Patricia M. A.; Cardozo, Olavo D. F.; Stingl, Andreas	PHORNANO	NanoWeek 2022		NO	Green Open Access	10.5281/zenodo.6793572	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6793572	2022	NA	253	NA
5	Publication in conference proceedings/workshop	Life-cycle Risk Assessment of Consumer Applications of Graphene: Outcomes, Data Gaps and Priorities	Ede, James D; Diges, Ana; Shatkin, Jo Anne	VIREO	Society for Risk Analysis Annual Meeting, 2022 (SRA 2022)		No	Green Open Access	10.5281/zenodo.8148725	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8148725	2022	NA	65	NA

6	Other	International Network Initiative on Safe and Sustainable Nanotechnologies (INISS-nano)	Falk, Andreas	BNN			No	Green Open Access	10.5281/zenodo.5004929	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5004929	2021	NA	4505	NA
7	Other	International Network Initiative on Safe and Sustainable Nanotechnologies (INISS-nano): revised concept and action plan	Falk, Andreas	BNN		1	No	Green Open Access	10.5281/zenodo.5004929	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5004929	2022	NA	4499	NA
8	Other (Poster)	Life-Cycle Risk Assessment of Graphene Functional Fabrics	Ede, James; Diges, Ana; Shatkin, Jo Anne	VIREO	NanoWeek 2022		NO	Green Open Access	10.5281/zenodo.6786748	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6786748	2022	NA	289	NA
9	Other (Poster)	Nanosized copper-based catalyst for automotive: physicochemical characterization	Soto, Amaia; Moschovi, Anastasia Maria; Mathioudakis, Georgios; Kourtelesis, Marios; Lada, Zoi; Andrikopoulos.	FORTH, MONOLITHOS	NanoWeek 2022		NO	Green Open Access	10.5281/zenodo.6772583	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6772583	2022	NA	482	NA
10	Other (Poster)	"First principles study of Co-Catalysed MgH ₂ for CO ₂ capture and conversion"	Rosas Azcona, Sara	UBU	FEMS Euromat Junior Congress		NO	Green Open Access	10.5281/zenodo.7716116	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7716116	2022	NA	70	NA
END OF REPORTING PERIOD 1: 3 journal articles, 3 posters, 2 conference presentations, 2 concept papers												5.254	15814	8
11	Article in Journal	One step before synthesis: structure-property-condition relationship models to sustainable design of efficient TiO ₂ -based multicomponent nanomaterials	Mikolajczyk, A.; Falkowski, D.	QSAR	International Journal of Molecular Sciences.	23(21): 13196.	Yes	Gold Open Access	10.3390/ijms232113196	https://www.mdpi.com/1422-0067/23/21/13196/htm	2022	6.2	1499	0
12	Article in Journal	Status, implications and challenges of European safe and sustainable by design paradigms applicable to nanomaterials and advanced materials	Irini Furxhi, Carlos Fito-L'opez, Juan Antonio Tamayo Ramos, Susanne Resch, Lucian Farca, et al.	BNN, ICCRAM	RSC Sustainability	2023	Yes	Gold Open Access	10.1039/D2SU00101B	https://doi.org/10.1039/D2SU00101B	2023	NA	338	17

13	Article in Journal	Core, coating, or corona? The importance of considering protein coronas in nano-QSPR modeling of zeta potential	Selvaraj Sengottayan, Alicja Mikolajczyk*, Karolina Jagiello, Marta Swirog, and Tomasz Puzyn	QSARLab	ACS Nano	2023	Yes	Gold Open Access	10.1021/acsnano.2c06977	https://doi.org/10.1021/acsnano.2c06977	2023	17.1	3382	2
14	Article in Journal	Retrosynthesis from transforms to predictive sustainable chemistry and nanotechnology: a brief tutorial review	Alicja Mikolajczyk, Uladzislau Zhdan, Sylvain Antoniotti, Adam Smolinski, Karolina Jagiello, Piotr Skurski, Moussab Harb, Tomasz Puzyn, Jaroslaw Polanski	QSARLab	Green Chemistry	2023	Yes	Gold Open Access	10.1039/D2GC04750K	https://doi.org/10.1039/D2GC04750K	2023	9.8	37	6
15	Article in Journal	Carbon nanomaterials with Thymol + Menthol Type V natural deep eutectic solvent: From surface properties to nano-Venturi effect through nanopores	Nuria Aguilar Cuesta, Rocio Barros Garcia, Juan Antonio Tamayo Ramos, Sonia Martel Martin, Alfredo Bol Arriba, Mert Athilan, & Santiago Aparicio Martinez.	ICCRAM / UBU	Journal of Molecular Liquids		Yes	Gold Open Access	10.1016/j.molliq.2022.120637	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.molliq.2022.120637	2022	6 633	30	4
16	Article in Journal	Thiosemicarbazonecopper /Halido Systems: Structure and DFT Analysis of the Magnetic Coupling	Jiménez-Pérez, Alondra, Sara Marcos-Gómez, Gotzon Madariaga, Manuel Zapico, Pablo Vitoria, Javier Tercero, M. Begoña Torres, Luis Lezama, José Vicente Cuevas, Iñigo Etxebarria, and et al.	UBU	Inorganics	Dec 2022	Yes	Gold Open Access	10.3390/inorganics11010031	https://doi.org/10.3390/inorganics11010031	2022	3 149	2928	1
17	Article in Journal	Life-cycle risk assessment of graphene-enabled textiles in fire protection gear	James D. Ede, Ana S. Diges, Yueyang Zhang, Jo Anne Shatkin,	Vireo	NanoImpact	Jan 2024	Yes	Gold Open Access	10.1016/j.impact.2023.100488	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.impact.2023.100488	2024	6 038	12	1

18	Article in Journal	Raman Spectroscopy Unfolds the Fate and Transformation of SWCNTs after Abrasive Wear of Epoxy Floor Coatings	Soto Beobide Amaia, Rudolf Bieri, Zoltán Szakács, Kevin Sparwasser, Ioanna G. Kaitsa, Ilias Georgiopoulos, Konstantinos S. Andrikopoulos, Gunther Van Kerckhove, and George A. Voyiatzis	FORTH, OCSIAL	Nanomaterials	14 (1)	Yes	Gold Open Access	10.3390/nano14010120	https://doi.org/10.3390/nano14010120	2024	5.4	2394	1
19	Article in Journal	An ancestral molecular response to nanomaterial particulates	del Giudice, G., Serra, A., Saarimäki, L.A. et al.	QSAR Lab, Novamechanics	Nature Nanotechnology	18, pages 957–966	Yes	Gold Open Access	10.1038/s41565-023-01393-4	https://doi.org/10.1038/s41565-023-01393-4	2023	38.3	8411	15
20	Article in Journal	How Does the Study MD of pH-Dependent Exposure of Nanoparticles Affect Cellular Uptake of Anticancer Drugs?	Sengottiyar, S.; Mikolajczyk, A.; Puzyn, T.	QSAR Lab	International Journal of Molecular Sciences.		Yes	Gold Open Access	10.3390/ijms24043479	https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms24043479	2023	6.2	1914	2
21	Other (Poster)	Development of an approach to characterize nanoparticles toxicity in the environment through toxicokinetics and toxicodynamics analysis in biofilms pseudomonas putida	DALIA DE LA FUENTE VIVAS, SARA COLLADO FERNANDEZ, NATALIA FERNANDEZ PAMPIN, NANDITA DASGUPTA, LAURA GOMEZ CUADRADO, MARTA BACCARO, Nico W. van den Brink, ROCIO BARROS GARCIA, SONIA MARTEL MARTIN, JUAN ANTONIO TAMAYO RAMOS, & CARLOS RUMBO LORENZO	ICCRAM, WUR	Spanish Society for Microbiology		No	Green Open Access	10.5281/zenodo.8042591	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8042591	2023	NA	123	NA

22	Other (Poster)	In vitro assessment of skin irritation potential of graphene based materials using reconstructed human epidermis (RhE)	NATALIA FERNANDEZ PAMPIN, JUAN ANTONIO TAMAYO RAMOS, NANDITA DASGUPTA, DALIA DE LA FUENTE VIVAS, ROCIO BARROS GARCIA, SONIA MARTEL MARTIN, LAURA GOMEZ CUADRADO, & CARLOS RUMBO LORENZO	ICCRAM	nanoSAFE and NanoSafety Cluster Joint Conference	No	Green Open Access	10.5281/zenodo.8042645	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8042645	2023	NA	91	NA
23	Other (Poster)	NanoConstruct: A toolbox for the digital reconstruction of Energy Minimized NanoParticles, Nanosheets and NanoTubes Powered by Enalos Cloud Platform	Panagiotis D. Kolokathis, Nikolaos K. Sidiropoulos, Andreas Tsoumanis, Anastasios G. Papadiamantis, Iseult Lynch, & Antreas Afantitis	NovaM	nanoSAFE and NanoSafety Cluster Joint Conference	No	Green Open Access	10.5281/zenodo.8039391	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8039391	2023	NA	82	NA
24	Other (Poster)	Exploring RNA-seq normalization methods using principal component analysis and KEGG pathway enrichment	Henk J. van Lingen, Maria Suarez-Diez and Edoardo Saccenti	WUR	BioSB 2023 conference proceedings	No	Green Open Access		https://zenodo.org/records/10528478		NA	80	NA
25	Other (Poster)	Study of the toxicity and the antimicrobial activity of different forms of ZnO nanoparticles	Natalia Fernández-Pampín ¹ , Rocío Barros ¹ , Sonia Martel Martín ¹ , Olavo Cardozo ^{2,3} , Andreas Stingl ² , Patricia Farias ^{2,4} , Alejandra García-Gómez ⁵ , Elisa Peña ⁵ , Carlos Rumbo ¹ , Juan Antonio Tamayo-Ramos ¹	ICCRAM	Week of Microbial Technologies	No	Green Open Access	10.5281/zenodo.7716143	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7716143	2022	NA	106	NA

26	Other (Poster)	Development of a methodology to perform toxicokinetics and toxicodynamics studies in biofilms	Carlos Rumbo1, Sara Collado1, Juan José González-Plaza1, Dalia de la Fuente-Vivas1, Natalia Fernández-Pampín1, Marta Baccaro2, Nico W. van den Brink2, Rocío Barros1, Sonia Martel Martín1, Juan Antonio Tamayo-Ramos1.	ICCRAM, WUR	International Congress of the European Society of Toxicology In Vitro (ESTIV 2022)	No	Green Open Access	10.5281/zenodo.7716087	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7716087	2022	NA	101	NA
27	Publication in conference proceedings/workshop	Zinc oxide nanoparticles: in silico characterization and toxicological risk assessment	Nuria Aguilar Cuesta, Sara Rozas Azcona, Elisabeth Escamilla Roa, Carlos Rumbo-Lorenzo, Sonia Martel Martin, Rocío Barros García, Pedro Angel Marcos Villa, Alfredo Bol Arreba, & Santiago Aparicio Martínez	ICCRAM / UBU	nanoSAFE'23 and NanoSafetyCluster joint conference	No	Green Open Access	10.5281/zenodo.8042806	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8042806	2023	NA	51	NA
END OF RP 2: 10 journal articles, 7 posters, 1 abstract											10.98	21579	49
TOTAL CUMULATIVE											9.548	37393	57
28	Article in Journal	Similarity of multicomponent nanomaterials in a safer-by-design context: the case of core-shell quantum dots		QSARLab	Environmental Science: nano	Yes	Gold Open Access	10.1039/D3EN00338H	https://doi.org/10.1039/D3EN00338H	2024	5.8	109	4
29	Article in Journal	Comparative toxicological analysis of two pristine carbon nanomaterials (graphene oxide and aminated graphene oxide) and their corresponding degraded forms using human in vitro models		UBU	Toxicology	Yes	Gold Open Access	10.1016/j.tox.2024.154153783	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tox.2024.154153783	2024	4.8	34	1

30	Article in Journal	Toxicology assessment of manganese oxide nanomaterials with enhanced electrochemical properties using human in vitro models representing different exposure routes		UBU	Toxicology		Yes	Gold Open Access	10.1038/s41598-022-25483-w	https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-022-25483-w	2022	5.1	1669	10
31	Article in Journal	Toxicological assessment of pristine and degraded forms of graphene functionalized with MnOx nanoparticles using human in vitro models representing different exposure routes		UBU	Toxicology		Yes	Gold Open Access	10.1038/s41598-023-38993-y	https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-023-38993-y	2023	5.1	1072	2
32	Article in Journal	Desulfurization of thiosemicarbazones: the role of metal ions and biological implications	Alondra Jiménez-Pérez, Sandra Fernández-Fariña, Rosa Pedrido, Javier García-Tojal	ICCRAM	JBIC Journal of Biological Inorganic Chemistry	29	Yes	Gold	10.1007/s00775-023-02037-7	https://doi.org/10.1007/s00775-023-02037-7	2023	3.1	508	2
33	Article in Journal	Next Generation Risk Assessment approaches for advanced nanomaterials: Current status and future perspectives	Danail Hristozov, Elisa Moschini, Carlos Rumbo, Otmar Schmid, Neeraj Shandilya, Vicki Stone, Stella Stoycheva, Tobias Stoeger, Blanca Suarez Merino, Lang Tran, Georgia Tsiliki, Ulla Birgitte Vogel, Wendel Wohlleben, Alex Zabeo et al.	ICCRAM, LIST	NanoImpact		Yes	Gold	10.1016/j.impact.2024.100523	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.impact.2024.100523	2024	4.7	143	2
34	Article in Journal	Theoretical multiscale study on the properties, aqueous solution behavior and biological impact of zinc oxide nanoparticles	AGUILAR, N., Rozas Azcona, S., Escamilla, E., Rumbo, C., Martel, S., Barros, R., Marcos Villa, P. Á., Bol-Arreba, A., & Aparicio, S.	ICCRAM	Surfaces and Interfaces		Yes	Gold Open Access	10.1016/j.surfin.2024.103965	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.surfin.2024.103965	2024	5,70	22	1

35	Other	Roadmap Towards Safe and Sustainable Advanced and Innovative Materials 2024-2030	Flemming R. Cassee, Eric A.J. Bleeker, Cyrille Durand, Thomas Exner, Andreas Falk, Danail Hristozov, Sabine Hofer, Norbert Hofstätter, Steffi Friedrichs, Elisabeth Heunisch, Martin Himly, Penny Nymark, Anna Pohl, Lya G. Soeteman-Hernández, Blanca Suarez-Merino, Eugenia Valsami-Jones, & Monique Groenewold.	BNN			No	Green Open Access	10.5281/zenodo.10980019	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10980019	2024	NA	1404	NA
36	Other (Poster)	NMBP-16 Ambassadors - Cooperation as cornerstone of our success	Alfaro Serrano, B., Resch, S., Hristozov, D., Schmid, O., Stöger, T., & Rumbo, C.	BNN, ICCRAM	NanoTox 2024 conference (NANOTOX 2024)		No	Green Open Access	10.5281/zenodo.13908183	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13908183	2024	NA	26	NA
Accepted		A systematic review on the state-of-the-art and research gaps regarding inorganic and carbon-based multicomponent and high-aspect ratio nanomaterials.												
Accepted		NanoBioAccumulate: Modelling the uptake and bioaccumulation of nanomaterials in soil and aquatic invertebrates via the Enalos DIAGONAL Cloud Platform.												
Accepted		NanoTube Construct: A Web Tool for the Digital Construction of Nanotubes of Single-Layer Materials.												

In progress	Minimising data needs to support the safe-by-design of multicomponent nanomaterials – Application of grouping	Stone V., Moschini E., Murphy F., Hunt N., Blosi M., Hristozov D., Johnston H., Stenton F., Mikolajczyk A., Oomen A.G., Schmid O., Tsiliki G., Vogel U., Wohlleben W.	Materials Today							2024			
In progress	MCDA-assisted environmental, economic and social-organisational life cycle assessments (LCA, LCC and SO-LCA) of the green production process of Mn-doped ZnO nanoparticles		UBU							2024			
In progress	In Silico Exploration of Graphene Nanoflakes: From DFT Simulations to Machine Learning-Driven Toxicity Predictions		UBU+ ISQ, LIST and 4N collaboration							2024			
In progress	Titanium Carbide Nanoparticles: Bridging the Gap Between Material Properties and Biological Impact		UBU, CNRS and ITENE							2024			
In progress	Multiscale Modelling on the nature and biological interactions of silver nanowires		UBU +							2024			
In progress	Biodegradation of carbon nanomaterials by environmental oxidative enzymes: the impact of material composition		UBU, CNRS and ITENE							2024			
In progress	Diffusion-enhanced efficiency of perovskite solar cells		PHORNANO							2024			
TOTAL RP 3: 7 journal articles, 1 poster, 1 other article										4.9	4987	22	
TOTAL PROJECT										7.84	42380	79	